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Hardware implementation of OFDM channel estimation

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ABSTRACT

Channel estimation and equalization is an essential part of present wireless communication systems. Wireless channels are usually difficult to track and estimate than the wire line channels. Two main challenges exist in wireless channels which are multipath fading and Doppler spread. Orthogonal frequency division multiplexing is a modulation as well as multiplexing technique which is now widely used in various high speed mobile and wireless communication systems because of its capacity of ensuring high level robustness against interference. In this paper, deferent channel estimation techniques for orthogonal frequency division multiplexing systems are studied and examined. Simulations are carried out for widely used channel estimation techniques and they are to be compared with respect to their bit error rates and mean square errors. Further, the orthogonal frequency division multiplexing system with 64-QAM is also implemented to study the effect of various design parameters on the system performance via computer simulations. All modules are designed using VHDL programming language.

Keywords: Bit error rate, channel estimation, multipath fading, orthogonal frequency division multiplexing.

I. INTRODUCTION

The basic principle of orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) is to split the high rate data stream into a number of lower rate streams that are transmitted simultaneously over a number of subcarriers [4-5]. Because the symbol duration increases for the lower rate parallel subcarriers, the relative amount of dispersion in time caused by the multipath delay spread is decreased. Inter symbol interference is eliminated almost completely by introducing guard time in every OFDM symbol. In the guard time the OFDM symbol is cyclically extended to avoid inter carrier interference.

Multipath fading and Doppler spread are two main challenges in wireless channels [1-3]. Multipath fading represents the selectivity of the channel and as the delay spread of the channel increases, the frequency selectivity increases, and the channel changes rapidly between adjacent subcarriers. As the

mobility of the user increases, the Doppler shift increases, and the channel is less correlated in time. These effects usually limit the wireless systems and cause very high bit error rates if not estimated and equalized correctly.

In OFDM system design, a number of parameters are up for consideration, such as the number of subcarriers, guard time, symbol duration, subcarrier spacing, modulation type per subcarrier, and the type of forward error correction coding [3]. The choice of parameters is influenced by system requirements such as available bandwidth, required bit rate, tolerable delay spread, and Doppler values. Some requirements are conflicting. For instance, to get a good delay spread tolerance, a large number of subcarriers with small subcarrier spacing are desirable, but the opposite is true for a good tolerance against Doppler spread and phase noise.

In this paper, deferent channel estimation techniques for OFDM systems are implemented. Simulations are carried out for different channel estimation techniques.

II. OFDM SYSTEM

The block diagram of an OFDM modem is shown in Fig. 1, where the upper path is the transmitter and the lower path corresponds to the receiver. IFFT block modulates a block of input QAM values onto a number of subcarriers. In the receiver the subcarriers are demodulated by an FFT block, which performs the reverse operation of an IFFT. This makes it possible to use the same hardware for both transmitter and receiver. This is possible only when the modem does not have transmit and receive at the same time.

In the receiver, after passing the radio frequency (RF) block and analog to digital conversion (ADC) blocks, digital signal processing starts with a training phase to determine the symbol timing and frequency offset. The output of the FFT contains N_s QAM values, which are mapped on to binary values, and decoded to produce binary output data to successfully map the QAM values onto binary values. First the reference phases and the amplitudes of all the subcarriers are acquired. Alternatively, differential techniques can also be applied.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of OFDM transceiver.

III. PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

The implemented channel estimation algorithm is the cascaded time interpolation frequency filtering method described in [6], which is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Cascaded Interpolation/Filtering Method.

Fig. 2 shows the pilot structure for each cluster in WiMAX. Each row represents a portion of the OFDM symbol called a cluster, and this unit is repeated along the whole OFDM symbol.

The estimation method is basically done in two steps. First of all, the pilots are interpolated in time to obtain accurate estimations at the in-between subcarriers.

In this paper, the interpolation is simply an averaging operation. Extrapolation is done on the edges to get the estimations at the first and the last OFDM symbols of the frame.

These accurate estimations are used as extra pilots added to the original pilots set available in each symbol. All these pilots and added pilots are available at the input to an FIR filter that estimates the remaining channels in between along each symbol.

Simulation results were obtained for different channel conditions. The overall performance is very good, taking into consideration the simplicity of the algorithm compared to other algorithms.

Fig. 3 shows a general block diagram of the whole system. The system should interface with the FFT block which is available in the receiver, extracts the pilots and separates them from the data. The data path is as follows:

The FFT engine starts producing its output, and its valid signal is raised high. This is the starting ignition of blocks. The least squares (LS) preparation block is responsible for separating the pilots and the data subcarriers into separate memories. The pilots are stored in two memories successively, i.e. the pilots of the first two symbols are stored in order in the first memory, and then the pilots in the third and fourth symbols are stored in the second memory and so on. The data subcarriers are stored in order in a different memory. It is assumed that the FFT output is produced in natural order.

Before the LS preparation block stores the pilots, it normalizes them by multiplying them by their well-known magnitude, in order that the subsequent filtering operation is correctly performed (which is known as LS). The data subcarriers are stored as they are without any normalization.

The interpolation and sorting block is responsible for interpolating the subcarriers in time to obtain the new subcarriers in between which will be used as extra pilots in the filtering operation. Interpolation is a simple averaging operation. At the symbol edges, interpolation is replaced by extrapolation. The interpolation is made simply by accessing the pilots RAM1 and RAM2 with the same address, and interpolating the output data from the two memories together.

The Interpolation and Sorting block is responsible for sorting the pilots all together in a single RAM, so that the filtering block can perform its operation easily. The original pilots are copied from RAM1 and RAM2 and are stored in their correct location in a new RAM. The interpolated data is also stored in the appropriate location. This sorting operation is clarified later.

The filtering block filters the sorted pilots to obtain the final channel estimator. It is complex multiply accumulate operation that is performed many times depending on the number of taps for the filter (for simulations 15 taps were used). The coefficients are stored in a RAM inside the block, and are loaded when needed.

Finally, the equalizer gets the filtering output as well as the original received data from the FFT which was stored before. The main function of this block is to

divide these two complex quantities by each other (to eliminate the channel effect from the received data, so subsequent demodulation, decoding, and detection can work properly).

As shown in Fig. 3, the main inputs to the system are the FFT output signals, and 4 different clock signals, one for each block. The main outputs are the final equalized data, its location, and its symbol number.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

Simulations are carried out to study the designed OFDM system. In Fig. 4, bit error rate (BER) versus signal to noise ratio (SNR) comparisons are made for different estimation techniques and found perfect estimation technique provide better gains.

In Fig. 5, mean squared error (MSE) versus signal to noise ratio (SNR) comparisons are made for different estimation techniques and found fixed point rounding estimation technique provide better gains.

Fig. 4. BER Comparisons for Hardware Verification.

Fig. 5. MSE Comparisons for Hardware Verification

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper, simulation model as well as hardware architecture of a channel estimation and equalization technique for WiMAX as a special case to the general

OFDM systems case is presented. Further, different channel estimation techniques currently used (estimation techniques based on Wiener Filtering and simple interpolations) are investigated.

Simulations proved that the resulting mean square error is not changed if there is a mismatch in the SNR used while calculating the filter coefficients.

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Fig. 3. Block diagram of the proposed system.

Blind Multiuser Detection in Asynchronous DS-CDMA Systems over Nakagami- m Fading Channels

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a technique for blind multiuser detection in asynchronous direct sequence-code division multiple access (DS-CDMA) systems over Nakagami- m fading channels with impulsive noise. A new M -estimator is proposed and analyzed for robustifying the detector. A closed-form expression for average error rate of DPSK signals is derived. Average probability of error is computed to evaluate the performance of the new M -estimator based blind multiuser detector in comparison with the linear decorrelating detector, Huber and Hampel estimator based detectors. Simulation results show that the new M -estimator based detector performs well.

Keywords: CDMA; impulsive noise; M -estimator; multiuser detection; Nakagami- m distribution; probability of error.

I. INTRODUCTION

Blind multiuser detection can be used to reduce the inter-symbol interference (ISI) and also to improve system performance [1]. Subspace-based blind multiuser detection technique is known for its better performance among all the other blind methods. In [2], an improved subspace-based robust blind multiuser detection technique for synchronous and asynchronous CDMA systems over non-Gaussian channels is presented. A new adaptive algorithm for blind multiuser detection of coherent BPSK signals in DS-CDMA systems operating under non-Gaussian impulsive noise is presented in [1]. The problem of robust multiuser detection in non-Gaussian channels has been addressed in the literature [3], which was developed based on the Huber and the Hampel M -estimators, respectively. Differential non-coherent data detection for CDMA over flat-fading non-Gaussian channels with impulsive noise is presented in [2], [4]. Robust multiuser detection in

synchronous DS-CDMA system with MRC receive diversity over Nakagami- m fading channel is presented in [5] by assuming that the modulation is binary PSK (BPSK). But, the differential modulation must be used to overcome the phase ambiguity [1], [4]. Recently, [6] considered the robust blind multiuser detection for synchronous DS-CDMA systems over Nakagami- m fading channels.

This paper extends the work of [6] to asynchronous DS-CDMA systems over Nakagami- m channels in the presence of heavy-tailed impulsive noise by employing subspace-based blind multiuser detection technique. An approximate expression for average probability of error of an M -decorrelator derived in [6] by using an approximation to Marcum-Q function. In this paper, a closed-form exact expression for average error rate is derived using [Eq. 3, 7]. This expression is used to compute the probability of error of linear decorrelating detector,

the Huber and the Hampel estimator based detectors, and the newly (modified-Hampel) proposed M -estimator based detector. Simulation results shows that the new M -estimator based detector outperforms the linear decorrelating detector, Huber and Hampel estimator based detectors.

The remaining part of the paper is organized as: DS-CDMA system over multipath fading channel in impulsive noise environment is presented in Section II. In Section III, new M -estimator proposed to robustify the detector is presented. Section IV presents the subspace-based robust blind multiuser detection technique. An expression for average probability of error of M -decorrelator is derived in Section V. Section VI, presents the simulation results and finally, conclusions are drawn in Section VII.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

An asynchronous DS-CDMA system shared by L -users, where each user transmits information by modulating a signature sequence over a single-path Nakagami- m fading channel, is considered. The received signal over one symbol duration can be modeled, when the users are symbol and chip asynchronous, as [4]:

$$r(t) = \Re \left\{ \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{i=0}^{M-1} b_l(i) \alpha_l(t) e^{j\theta_l(t)} s_l(t - iT_s - \tau_l) \right\} + n(t) \quad (1)$$

where $\Re\{\cdot\}$

denotes the real part, M is the number of data symbols per user in the data frame of interest, T_s is the symbol interval, $\alpha_l(t)$ is the time-varying fading gain of the l^{th} user's channel, $\theta_l(t)$ is the time-varying phase of the l^{th} user's channel, $b_l(i)$ is the i^{th} bit of the l^{th} user, $s_l(t)$ is the normalized signaling waveform of the l^{th} user, τ is the propagation delay and $n(t)$ is assumed as a zero-mean complex non-Gaussian noise given by [3]

$$f = (1 - \varepsilon) \mathfrak{N}(0, \nu^2) + \varepsilon \mathfrak{N}(0, \kappa \nu^2) \quad (2)$$

with $\nu > 0$, $0 \leq \varepsilon \leq 1$, and $\kappa \geq 1$.

Here $\mathfrak{N}(0, \nu^2)$ represents the nominal background noise and the $\mathfrak{N}(0, \kappa \nu^2)$ represents an impulsive component, with ε representing the probability that impulses occur. At the receiver, the received signal $r(t)$ is first filtered by a chip-matched filter and then sampled at the chip rate, $1/T_c$. The resulting discrete-time signal sample corresponding to the n^{th} chip of the i^{th} symbol is given by [4]

$$r_n(i) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{T_c}} \int_{iT_s+nT_c}^{iT_s+(n+1)T_c} r(t) e^{-j\omega_c t} dt, n = 1 \dots N. \quad (3)$$

Assuming that the fading process for each user varies at a slower rate that the phase and amplitude can taken to be constant over the duration of a bit, (3) simplifies to [4]

$$r_j(i) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{l=1}^L \left[g_l(i) b_l(i) h_j^l(0) + g_l(i-1) b_l(i-1) h_j^l(1) \right] + w_j(i) \quad (4)$$

where

$$h_j^l(0) \triangleq \begin{cases} 0, & j < m_l \\ (1 - \pi_l) a_{j-m_l}^l, & j = m_l \\ \pi_l a_{j-m_l-1}^l + (1 - \pi_l) a_{j-m_l}^l, & j > m_l \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$$h_j^l(1) \triangleq \begin{cases} \pi_l a_{j+N-m_l-1}^l + (1 - \pi_l) a_{j+N-m_l}^l, & j < m_l \\ \pi_l a_{j-m_l+N-1}^l, & j = m_l \\ 0, & j > m_l \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

with $m_l \equiv \left\lceil \frac{\tau_l}{T_c} \right\rceil$, $\pi_l \equiv \frac{\tau_l}{T_c} - m_l$ and

$$w_j(i) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{T_c}} \int_{iT_s+jT_c}^{iT_s+(j+1)T_c} n(t) e^{-j\omega_c t} dt. \quad (7)$$

Let $\underline{r}(i) \triangleq [r_0(i), \dots, r_{N-1}(i)]^T$, $\underline{w}(i) \triangleq [w_0(i), \dots, w_{N-1}(i)]^T$ and $\underline{\theta}(i) \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} [b_1(i)g_1(i), \dots, b_L(i)g_L(i)]^T$. By stacking k successive data samples, the following quantities can be defined [2], [4],

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{r}_k(i) &\equiv \begin{bmatrix} \underline{r}(i) \\ \vdots \\ \underline{r}(i+k-1) \end{bmatrix}_{kN}, \quad \underline{\theta}_k(i) \equiv \begin{bmatrix} \underline{\theta}(i-1) \\ \underline{\theta}(i) \\ \vdots \\ \underline{\theta}(i+k-1) \end{bmatrix}_{(k+1)N} \quad (8) \\ \underline{w}_k(i) &\equiv \begin{bmatrix} \underline{w}(i) \\ \vdots \\ \underline{w}(i+k-1) \end{bmatrix}_{kN} \end{aligned}$$

and $\underline{r}_k(i)$ can be written as

$$\underline{r}_k(i) = \underline{H}_k(i)\underline{\theta}_k(i) + \underline{w}_k(i), \quad (9)$$

where

$$\underline{H}_k(i) \equiv \begin{bmatrix} \underline{H}(1) & \underline{H}(0) & \underline{0} & \cdot & \cdot & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \underline{0} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \underline{0} & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \underline{H}(1) & \underline{H}(0) \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

with

$$\underline{H}(0) \equiv \begin{bmatrix} h_1^L(0) & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & h_1^L(0) \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ h_N^L(0) & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & h_N^L(0) \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

and

$$\underline{H}(1) \equiv \begin{bmatrix} h_1^L(1) & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & h_1^L(1) \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ h_N^L(1) & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & h_N^L(1) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

The parameter k is called the smoothing factor and is chosen such that the matrix \underline{H}_k has full column rank.

III. M- ESTIMATOR

There exist in the literature a number of different approaches to the robust estimation problem, and the M -estimation is one of the most sophisticated approaches to this problem [8]. An important class of robust estimators is M -estimators and they can resist outliers without preprocessing the data [9]. In

M -estimates, unknown parameters $\underline{\theta}_1, \underline{\theta}_2, \dots, \underline{\theta}_L$ are solved by minimizing a sum of function $\rho(\cdot)$ of the residuals [4]

$$\hat{\underline{\theta}} = \arg \min_{\underline{\theta} \in C^L} \sum_{n=1}^N \left\{ \rho \left[\Re \left(\underline{r}_n(i) - \sum_{l=1}^L [\underline{A}]_{nl} \theta_l(i) \right) \right] + \rho \left[\Im \left(\underline{r}_n(i) - \sum_{l=1}^L [\underline{A}]_{nl} \theta_l(i) \right) \right] \right\} \quad (13)$$

where ρ is a symmetric positive-definite function with a unique minimum at zero, and is chosen to be less increasing than square, $r_n(i)$ and $\theta_l(i)$ are the n^{th} and l^{th} elements of the vectors $\underline{r}(i)$ and $\underline{\theta}(i)$ respectively, $[\underline{A}]_{nl}$ is the nl^{th} element of the matrix \underline{A} [see 4 for details], and $\Im(\cdot)$ denotes imaginary part. Since least squares (LS) estimate is very sensitive to the tail behavior of the noise density, linear decorrelating multiuser detector is also sensitive to the tail behavior of the noise distribution. Hence, a new M -estimator [10] is used to deal with heavy-tailed noise. The influence function of new M -estimator is given by [10], [11]

$$\psi_{PRO}(\zeta) = \begin{cases} \zeta & \text{for } |\zeta| \leq a \\ a \operatorname{sgn}(\zeta) & \text{for } a < |\zeta| \leq b \\ \frac{a}{b} \zeta \exp \left(1 - \frac{|\zeta|^2}{b^2} \right) & \text{for } |\zeta| > b \end{cases}. \quad (14)$$

The choice of the constants $a (= \kappa v^2)$ and $b (= 2 \kappa v^2)$ depends on the robustness measures derived from the influence function.

IV. ROBUST BLIND MULTIUSER DETECTION

In robust blind multiuser detection for asynchronous channels the signal subspace components of the covariance matrix of the signal $\underline{r}_k(i)$ are computed as [2], [4]

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{C} &\equiv E[\underline{r}_l(i)\underline{r}_l(i)^T] = \underline{H}_k(i)\underline{W}_k^2\underline{H}_k^T + \nu\underline{I}_N \\ &= \underline{U}_s\underline{\Lambda}_s\underline{U}_s^T + \nu^2\underline{U}_n\underline{U}_n^T \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Here, the signal subspace has dimension of $L(m+1)$. Then, the robust estimation in the signal subspace follows as

$$r^k(i) \cong \psi(r - U_s \xi^k(i)) \quad (16)$$

$$\xi^{k+1}(i) = \xi^k(i) + \frac{1}{\mu} U_s^T r^k(i) \quad (17)$$

where μ is a step-size parameter chosen as $\frac{1}{\mu} = \nu^2$.

The estimate of the product of the amplitude and the data bit $\theta_l(i) = W_l b_l(i)$ of the l^{th} user is given by [4]

$$\theta_l(i) = \sum_{j=1}^{L(k+1)} \frac{u_j^T h_l}{\lambda_j} \xi_l(i), l=1,2,\dots,L \quad (18)$$

where $h_l \equiv [h_l^T \quad 0_{N(k-2)}^T]^T$ and finally, the l^{th} user data bit is demodulated as

$$\hat{b}_l(i+1) = \text{sgn} \left\{ \Re \left[\hat{\theta}_{k,2L+l}(i) \hat{\theta}_{k,2L+l}^*(i) \right] \right\}. \quad (19)$$

V. AVERAGE PROBABILITY OF ERROR OF M-DECORRELATOR

The asymptotic probability of error of non-coherent DPSK demodulator can be evaluated by averaging the conditional probability [4]

$$\begin{aligned} P \left(\Re \left\{ \hat{\theta}_l(i) \hat{\theta}_l^*(i-1) \right\} < 0 \mid \Delta \phi_l(i) = 0, x, y \right) \\ = Q_M \left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{2\sigma_{\hat{\theta}_l}^2}} x, \sqrt{\frac{1}{2\sigma_{\hat{\theta}_l}^2}} y \right) - \frac{1}{2} I_o \left(\frac{xy}{2\sigma_{\hat{\theta}_l}^2} \right) e^{-\frac{x^2+y^2}{4\sigma_{\hat{\theta}_l}^2}} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

over the joint probability density function (PDF) of the random variables x and y [4]. Here

$$\sigma_{\hat{\theta}_l}^2 \triangleq \frac{1}{N} \nu^2 \left[\underline{R}^{*-1} \right]_{ll} \quad (21)$$

with

$$\nu^2 = \frac{\int \psi^2(u) f(u) du}{\left[\int \psi'(u) f(u) du \right]^2} \quad (22)$$

and \underline{R}^* is the cross-correlation matrix of the random infinite-length signature waveforms of the L users, $Q_M(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the Marcum's Q -function and $I_o(\cdot)$ is the modified Bessel function of the first kind with order zero. Here, it is assumed that the random variables x and y are statistically independent and Nakagami- m distributed with PDF [12]. By following the steps as in [6] and using [Eq. 3, 7], the average probability of error of DPSK signals can be derived as (23) and shown at the end of the paper. In (23),

$$H = \frac{(1/4\sigma_{\hat{\theta}_l}^2)/(4m/\Omega+1/\sigma_{\hat{\theta}_l}^2)}{(m/\Omega+1/4\sigma_{\hat{\theta}_l}^2)}, {}_2F_1(\cdot)$$

is the Gauss hypergeometric function and $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the gamma function [13],

$$\Omega = \frac{1}{N} \left\{ \nu^2 \left[\underline{R}^{*-1} \right]_{ll} + 2SNR_l \sigma^2 (1 - \rho_l) \right\}, \quad (23)$$

$\sigma^2 = (1 - \varepsilon)\nu^2 + \varepsilon\kappa\nu^2$ (with ν^2 and $\kappa\nu^2$, respectively, as the variance of in-phase and quadrature components of noise samples) and

$$SNR_l \triangleq \frac{E \left[|g_l(i)|^2 \right]}{\sigma^2}. \quad (24)$$

VI. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, the performance of M -decorrelator is presented by computing (23) for different values of Nakagami fading parameter and different order of diversity. It is assumed that the channel model is a lightly damped second-order autoregressive (AR) process given by [4] with the bit rate, the pole radius, and the spectral peak frequencies are $T_b = 10$ kbps, $r_d = 0.998$ and $f_p = 80$ Hz, respectively. Further, it is also assumed that $M = 1$ in evaluating average probability of error, (23).

Performance of decorrelating detector with different influence functions is shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. In Fig. 1, the average probability of error versus the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) corresponding to the user 1 under perfect power control of an asynchronous DS-CDMA system with six users ($L = 6$) and a large processing gain, $N = 127$ is plotted for $m = 1$ and $D = 1$. Similarly, in Fig. 2, average probability of error is plotted for $m = 2$ and $D = 2$. The simulation results reveal that the increase in diversity order (from 1 to 2) improves the detector performance. Simulation results also reveals that the proposed M -estimator outperforms the linear decorrelating detector and minimax decorrelating detector (both with Huber and Hampel estimators), even in highly impulsive noise. Moreover, this performance gain increases as the SNR increases.

VII. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Blind multiuser detection in asynchronous DS-CDMA systems over Nakagami- m fading channels in an impulsive noise environment is presented. A new M -estimator (modified-Hampel) based blind multiuser detection technique is presented and its performance is analyzed by deriving a closed-form expression for average error rate. This expression is used to compute the average probability of error of the M -decorrelator with least-squares, Huber, Hampel and proposed M -estimators. Simulation results show that the blind multiuser detector offers significant performance gain over the linear multiuser detector and the minimax decorrelating detectors with Huber and Hampel M -estimators, in impulsive noise. Effect of fading parameter and diversity order on the performance of decorrelator is also studied.

Fig. 1. Average probability of error versus SNR for user 1 for linear multiuser detector (Least Squares), minimax detector with Huber, Hampel and proposed M -estimator in asynchronous DS-CDMA channel with moderate ($\epsilon = 0.01$) impulsive noise.

Fig. 2. Average probability of error versus SNR for user 1 for linear multiuser detector (Least Squares), minimax detector with Huber, Hampel and proposed M -estimator in asynchronous DS-CDMA channel with highly ($\epsilon = 0.1$) impulsive noise.

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$$\bar{P}_e^l = \frac{(m/\Omega)^{mD} \Gamma(mD+M)}{\left(m/\Omega+1/4\sigma_{\theta_i}^2\right)^{mD+M}} \left[\left(\frac{1/4\sigma_{\theta_i}^2}{m/\Omega+1/4\sigma_{\theta_i}^2}\right)^M {}_2F_1\left(1, mD+M; mD+1; (m/\Omega)/(m/\Omega+1/4\sigma_{\theta_i}^2)\right)/(mD)! \right. \\ \left. + \left(\frac{1/2\sigma_{\theta_i}^2}{m/\Omega+1/4\sigma_{\theta_i}^2}\right)^{mD-1} \sum_{i=0}^{mD-1} \frac{1}{M!(m/\Omega)^{mD-i} 2^{M-i+1} \left(2m/\Omega+1/2\sigma_{\theta_i}^2\right)^{i+1}} {}_2F_1(i+1, mD+M; H) \right] \\ + 0.5 {}_2F_1\left(mD, mD; 1; -1/(16\sigma_{\theta_i}^4)(\Omega/m)^2\right) \quad (25)$$

Cooperative Spectrum Sensing by Sequential Change Detection in Cognitive Radio

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes the solution for Spectrum Sensing Problems in Cognitive Radio Networks. For this an Adaptive CUSUM based Test for signal Change Detection algorithm is used. The algorithm is based on sequential change detection techniques which is particularly effective when the parameters are not available a-priori or when the correct parameter configuration and the pdf of the signal under test are unknown. This work provides an extension of the CUSUM algorithm which allows the test parameters to be configured. The proposed Adaptive CUSUM provides accuracy, change detection readiness and computational complexity.

Keywords: Cognitive Radio, change detection, spectrum sensing, Adaptive CUSUM.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cognitive Radio uses the radio spectrum of the other users. They perform radio environment analysis, identify the spectral holes and then operate in those holes. In cognitive radio terminology Primary user refers to a user who is allocated the rights to use the spectrum. Secondary user refers to the users who try to use the spectrum bands allocated to the primary user when the primary user is not using it [1].

Spectrum sensing is an essential component of the Cognitive Radio technology which involves, identifying spectrum holes, and when an identified spectrum hole is being used by the secondary users, to quickly detect the onset of primary transmission. This needs to be done such that the guaranteed interference levels to the primary are maintained and there is efficient use of spectrum by the secondary. This involves detecting reliably, quickly and robustly, possibly weak, primary user signals [1-2].

In practice, Spectrum Sensing becomes a challenging task because the channel from the primary transmitter to the secondary user can be bad because of shadowing and time varying multipath Fading. As a result, detecting the primary user based on the observation of a single secondary user may not be enough, especially under low SNR conditions.

Hence, Cooperative Spectrum Sensing is required, whereby the spatial diversity inherent in radio environment is leveraged by allowing multiple secondary users to cooperate. This reduces the average time to detect the primary user. This in turn lowers the interference to the primary user, while increasing the spectrum usage of the secondary user [2]. Depending on the amount of information about a primary user's parameters available at a cognitive user, various detection schemes have been developed for this application. In addition to the detection probability, the detection delay is also an important performance metric in cognitive radio detection. If a primary user stops transmission, then a secondary user should detect this event quickly, in order to be able to start its own transmission quickly. A small detection delay will allow the design of a spectrum reuse scheme that has minimal impact on the licensed users [5].

II. MODEL AND ALGORITHM

A) Model

Consider a Cognitive Radio System with L secondary users who sense a channel via Energy Detectors. The observations made on the channel by these users are processed and sent to a fusion center which makes a decision whether the channel is free or not. Then that decision is sent to all secondary users for possible use

of channel. The secondary nodes have to detect the change in the status of the channel in two situations. First, when the primary has been using the channel and it stops transmission. The secondary nodes have to cooperatively detect this change as soon as possible so that they can make maximum use of the available channel. The second situation is when the channel has been free and the secondaries are using the channel. They need to sense the channel to see if the primary starts transmission. It is difficult to detect this when the secondaries are transmitting, especially when the energy detection method is used. Thus, in between their transmissions, secondary's stop intermittently for a few slots and sense the channel to see if primary has started transmission. If yes the secondary's need to stop using that channel. To minimize interference to the primary, this also needs to be done quickly [1], [2].

The aim is to detect the change at the fusion center as soon as possible at a time τ using the messages transmitted from the L sensors with an upper bound on probability of false alarm. For this each of the L nodes uses its observation $X_{k,l}$ to generate a signal $Y_{k,l}$ and transmits to the Fusion Center. The data received at the fusion center is corrupted by the i.i.d. receiver noise Z_k at the fusion center. The fusion center uses the observations $Y_{k,1}, Y_{k,2}, \dots, Y_{k,L}$ to decide between the two hypotheses H_0 and H_1 . If H_0 is chosen the secondaries continue to use the channel in slot k and the spectrum sensing session continues. If H_1 is detected, the secondaries typically switch over to an alternate channel. To transmit $Y_{k,1}, Y_{k,2}, \dots, Y_{k,L}$ from the L secondaries to their fusion node, they need a Multiple Access Channel (MAC) protocol. Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA) is the most commonly used protocol. We will allow all nodes to transmit simultaneously and use physical layer fusion. This saves time in transmission [1].

III. COOPERATIVE SENSING ALGORITHMS

As explained in [1-2], DualCUSUM and CUSUM (developed in [3]) algorithms run at the local (secondary) nodes. If it crosses a threshold γ then it transmits a message to the fusion node. There is physical layer fusion at the fusion node of all the transmissions from different secondaries. The fusion node also runs CUSUM based on its input and finally declare a change if it's CUSUM process exceeds a threshold β .

A) DualCUSUM Algorithm

1) Each of the secondary users l runs Parametric CUSUM algorithm [1].

$$W_{k,l} = \max(0, W_{k-1,l} + \xi_{k,l}), W_{0,l} = 0$$

$$\text{where, } \xi_{k,l} = \log [f_{1,l}(X_{k,l})/f_0(X_{k,l})],$$

$f_{1,l}$ is the density of $X_{k,l}$ under H_1 and f_0 is the density of $X_{k,l}$ under H_0 .

2) Secondary user l transmit at time k , only if $W_{k,l} > \gamma$. The parameters b and γ are chosen appropriately. This censoring allows saving energy, and causing less interference to others.

3) At the fusion center we assume physical layer fusion: $\epsilon_k = \sum_l Y_{k,l} + Z_k$ where Z_k is i.i.d. noise at the fusion node.

4) Change detection at the fusion center via CUSUM:
 $\epsilon_k = \max\{0, F_{k-1} + \log \frac{g_1(Y_k)}{g_0(Y_k)}\}$ where g_0 is the density of Z_k and g_1 is the density of $Z_k + bI$, I being a design parameter.

5) The Fusion Center declares a change at time k when F_k crosses a threshold β :
 $k = \inf\{k: F_k > \beta\}$.

Though Dual CUSUM is probably not optimal, it has some desirable features:

- (i) it uses past observations at the local nodes as well at the fusion nodes;
- (ii) local nodes employ censoring before transmitting
- (iii) physical layer fusion is exploited in transmitting the data to fusion node [1-2].

B) Adaptive CUSUM Algorithm

Dual CUSUM assumes that both $f_{1,l}$ and f_0 are available. In Cognitive Radio the difficulty is in obtaining perfect knowledge of P_l , the primary's power and the noise power σ^2 [1], [2].

DualCUSUM algorithm used at the secondary nodes is replaced by the Adaptive CUSUM algorithm. Let the density of $X_{k,l}$ be f_0 before change and f_θ after change, where θ is a parameter that characterizes density after change.

To measure the discrepancy between the two pdfs at time t consider the log-likelihood ratio

$$s_t = \ln \frac{f_\theta(X_{k,l})}{f_0(X_{k,l})} \text{ for each } 1 \leq t \leq N$$

And evaluate the cumulative sum $S_t = \sum_{i=1}^t s_i$. CUSUM identifies a change in $X_{k,l}$ at time t^l when the difference g_t between the value of the cumulative sum S_t and its current minimum value m_t at time t^l is larger than a given threshold value β

$$g_t = S_t - m_t \geq h | \bar{t}, m_t = \min_{1 \leq i \leq t} (S_i).$$

Very rarely parameters f_θ , f_0 , and h are available at design-time. When this does not happen the designer has to provide an estimate based on a trial and error basis. In the following, we suggest a configuration procedure which allows the designer to automatically and adaptively identify the needed parameters. The procedure can be as follows:

- 1) Define the configuration sequence
- 2) Estimate the f_θ parameter
- 3) Evaluate the f_0 parameter
- 4) Evaluate the h parameter

Consider the first K instances of X (with $K < N$) as configuration sequence:
 $TS = \{x_i : 1 \leq i \leq K\}$.

To compute the log-likelihood ratio the knowledge of probability density function of the stochastic process is required. If it is not available, as it is mostly the case, we generate a cumulative sequence $Y = \{y_1, y_2, \dots\}$ from X .

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper an extension of CUSUM, Dual CUSUM is presented to change detection test to overcome the need to configure at design time the parameters. Automatic configuration of parameters is also proposed. A change detection approach was setup and the use of the adaptive approach is very appealing both when correct parameters are not available a-priori and when the pdf of the signal is not known. This approach is very useful in spectrum sensing of Cognitive Radio environments where the signal information is readily not available at the fusion center (suitable for cognitive radio systems).

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Mobility and Interference analysis of Downlink Long Term Evolution using System Level Simulation

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ABSTRACT

LTE (Long Term Evolution) or the E-UTRAN (Evolved Universal Terrestrial Access Network), introduced in 3GPP R8, is the access part of the Evolved Packet System (EPS). The main requirements for the new access network are high spectral efficiency, high peak data rates, short round trip time as well as flexibility in frequency and bandwidth. Performance of LTE depends on several parameters. This paper analyzes the impact of mobility and interference of users on the down link Long Term Evolution using System Level Simulator from [1]. The results obtained concern the sector throughput, BLER (Block Error Rate), the user throughput and the corresponding CQI (Channel Quality Indicator) during all simulation period. The scenarios used considered SISO antenna configuration, Round Robin packet scheduling algorithm and different number of users in the cell. Due to mobility and interference considerable user and sector throughput is observed.

Keywords: Block error rate, channel quality indicator, long term evaluation, and single input single output.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) has standardized Long Term Evolution (LTE) in Release-8 to build the framework for 3G evolution towards 4G. The motivation for 3G evolution came from the growing demand for network services such as VoIP, web browsing, video telephony, and video streaming, with constraints on delays and bandwidth requirements. LTE aims to support all the applications with better performance at reduced cost, besides maintaining seamless mobility [3]. LTE is an all-IP packet based system with design targets of Supporting high peak data rates of 100Mb/s in the downlink (DL) and 50 Mb/s in the uplink (UL), low latency (10ms round-trip delay), improved system capacity and coverage [3] [4].

To achieve the performance objectives, LTE employs the several enabling technologies which include

Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access (OFDMA), Single Carrier Frequency Division Multiple Access (SC-FDMA) [10] and Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO). LTE technology uses air interface based on OFDMA for downlink and SC-FDMA for uplink. The LTE operates in both Time Division Duplexing (TDD) and Frequency Division Duplexing (FDD) modes and can be deployed in a range of channel bandwidths up to 20MHz.

II. LTE DOWNLINK OVERVIEW

The LTE down link is mainly characterized by OFDMA as multiple access scheme and MIMO (Multiple Input Multiple Output) technology. The benefit of deploying OFDMA technology on down link LTE is the ability of allocating capacity on both time and frequency, allowing multiple users to be scheduled at a time. The minimum resource that can be assigned to a user consists of two Physical Resource Blocks (PRBs) and it is known as chunk or

simply Resource Block (RB). In downlink LTE one PRB is mapped on 12 subcarriers (180 kHz) and 7 OFDM symbols (0.5 ms) and this is true for non-MBSFN (Multimedia Broadcast multicast service Single Frequency Network) LTE systems and for normal CP (Cyclic Prefix).

Scheduling decisions can be made each TTI (Time Transmission Interval) that in LTE is equal to 1 ms [6]. System performance and individual end user experience depend on the propagation conditions, the mobile device feedback, which is based on measurements, and the scheduling algorithm in the eNodeB (Evolved NodeB). Packet Scheduling is one of LTE RRM (Radio Resource Management) functions, three packet scheduling algorithms are used: Round Robin (RR), Proportional Fair (PF) and Best CQI Round Robin (RR):The scheduler assigns resources cyclically to the users without taking channel conditions into account. This is a simple procedure giving the best fairness. But it would offer poor performance in terms of cell throughput. The best CQI scheduler tries to maximize total throughput and completely ignores fairness by just as signing resources to the users with the best channel conditions. The PF strategy is an intermediate strategy, fairer than the Best CQI strategy, but with higher global performances than the RR scheduling.

Simulators overview is presented in section II. System Level Simulation of Different scenarios are presented in the section III and Link Level Simulations are discussed in the section IV. Section V concludes the paper.

III LTE SIMULATOR OVERVIEW

System level simulation focus more on network-related issues, such as resource allocation and scheduling [2], multi-user handling, mobility management, admission control , interference management, and network planning optimization [2]. Schematic block diagram of the LTE system level simulator is depicted in Fig.1 [2]. The simulator consists of two parts: (i) a link measurement model, and (ii) a link performance model. The link measurement model reflects the link quality, given by the UE measurement reports, and is required to carry out link adaptation and resource allocation. The chosen link quality measure is evaluated per subcarrier [5]. Based on the Signal to Interference and Noise Ratio (SINR), the UE computes the feedback

(PMI, RI, and CQI), which is employed for link adaptation at the eNodeB. The scheduling algorithm assigns resources to users to optimize the performance of the system. Based on the link measurement model, the link performance model predicts the BLER of the link based on the receiver SINR and the transmission parameters (e.g., modulation and coding)[5]. Fig. 2 shows LTE BLER for CQIs 1 to 15 based on the receiver SINR.

Fig. 1 Schematic block diagram of the LTE system level simulator.

TABLE I: Simulation parameters

Parametrs	Assumptions
Carrier Frequency	2.1GHz
Transmission Bandwidth	5MHz
Thermal Noise Density	-174 dBm/ Hz
Inter-site distance	500m
Receiver noise figure	9 dB
Simulation length	500 TTI
UE speeds of interest	5km/hr
UEs position	UEs located in target sector Only, 20 UEs/sector
BS antenna gain	15 dBi
Scheduler	RR scheduler
Minimum coupling loss	70 dB
Tx mode	1
nTx x nRx antennas	1x1
eNodeB Tx power	43dBm

SINR Algorithm	Averaging	EESM,
Uplink delay	3	
Macroscopic path loss	$128.1 + 37.6\log_{10}(R)$	

Fig. 2. LTE BLER for CQIs 1 to 15.

IV. SIMULATION SCENARIOS AND RESULTS

For the first scenario simulated it was selected 2.1GHz as carrier frequency, 5 MHz system bandwidth, SISO antenna technology, RR scheduler, 10 UE per eNodeB sector, meaning 70 UEs, UEs speed 5 km/h, Typical Urban as channel model, inter eNodeB distance 500 m. The UEs are randomly positioned in the cells.

The sector throughput and BLER for each eNodeB are shown in Fig. 3. The throughput values vary from 0.01 Mbps to 18.05 Mbps due to the user position in the sector, the interference experimented from other users etc.

The second scenario was built in order to see the user speed influence on the throughput. Two things change from the previous scenario: UE speed (100 km/h). The sector throughput for this second scenario is illustrated in Fig. 4. Comparing Fig. 4 with Fig. 3 Moreover, the network BLER increases when the user speed is higher.

Fig. 3. Network BLER and throughput using 5 MHz transmission bandwidth and UEs speed 5 km/h.

Fig. 4. Network BLER and throughput using 5 MHz transmission bandwidth and UEs speed 100 km/h.

Fig. 5 represents the throughput and BLER report for UE 67 (the one from eNodeB 1, sector 2). There are two curves for BLER. The green line represents the BLER as measured by the ACK/NACK ratio and the black line – the values applied by the link quality model [1] and the CQI's values for UE 67. The blue line is the sent CQI report for the selected RB, the mean CQI for the whole frequency bandwidth is red and the CQI of the Transport Block sent to the UE is marked with black [1].

Fig. 5. Throughput and BLER, CQI report for UE 67 using 5MHz and RR scheduler with 10 users per eNodeB.

A third scenario was simulated to analyze the influence of interference as the number of users

increases in the system and a considerable decrease in the throughput is observed for network as well as for all the users in the network and shown in Fig 6 and Fig. 7. Fig 8 shows Network BLER and throughput using 5 MHz transmission bandwidth and 30 UEs per eNodeB and keeping all the parameters from scenario 1. The maximum sector throughput obtained in Fig. 6 is approximately quarter of the highest throughput value illustrated in Fig. 4. And user 100 throughput and BLER, CQI report is depicted in Fig 7.

Fig. 6. Network BLER and throughput using 5 MHz transmission bandwidth and RR scheduler with 30 users per eNodeB.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper evaluates the mobility and interference of downlink LTE using System Level Simulator. First, it was analyzed the impact of the users speed, for that several simulations has been done with different user speeds and is presented in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 with 5km/h and 100km/h, on comparing both figures, it is observed there was a strong decrease in user and sector throughput because the feedback cannot follow the fast fading. Second, it was analyzed the impact of interference on the users throughput and the network throughput when users are increased from 10 users per eNodeB to 30 users per eNodeB with Round Robin scheduling, and it is presented in Fig.3 and Fig. 6, considerable decrease in throughput to both users and network is observed because of multi cell interference. Individual user throughput is shown in Fig. 5 and Fig.7.

LTE performance depends on lots of parameters and configuration chosen, but through these simulations, several LTE expectations have been achieved.

Fig. 7. Throughput and BLER, CQI report for UE 6 using 5MHz and RR scheduler with 30 users per eNodeB.

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Design and Implementation of Carry Select Adder without using Multiplexer

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ABSTRACT

Design of high performance digital adder with reduced area and low power consumption is an important requirement in advanced digital processors for faster computation. In digital adder circuits, the speed of addition is limited by the time required for a carry to propagate through the adder. Many different approaches had already been suggested to improve the performance of the adder. Carry Select Adder is one among them and is used to solve the problem of carry propagation delay by independently generating multiple carries and then select a carry to generate the final sum. The speed of operation of such an adder is limited by carry propagation from input to output. Our work is based on designing an optimized adder for advanced processors. It discusses about the implementation of Carry Select Adder without using Multiplexer for final selection. Parallel adder configuration is also used to reduce the delay between stages. Removing the MUX stage will reduce the area as well as propagation delay to give much higher performance for the adder. The Kogge Stone parallel approach will generate fast carry for intermediate stages.

Keywords: CSA, MUX.

I. INTRODUCTION

This approach will reduce the problem of existing scheme and CSA [2] is one among them which will reduce the carry propagation delay problem. In CSA, requirement of producing two adders and final selection multiplexers make it consuming more area, even though carry propagation delay is reduced much. Buffering inverters are to be added appropriately to support these large loads and there is a corresponding increase in the delay. Brent & Kung [3] proposed the fan-out trees such that the lateral fan-out of each node is restricted to unity, as for the Kogge Stone graph, but without the explosion of wires.

Although looks attractive it increases the logical depth. This illustrates the approach of carry select adder implementation to achieve minimum delay and reduced area without increasing the fan-out.

II. RIPPLE CARRY ADDER

There are many carry select adder approaches available but most of them use ripple carry adders [1] to implement the adder.

Disadvantages of existing system

- Delay is more.
- It requires more area.
- Power consumption is more
-

In electronics, an adder or summer is a digital circuit that performs addition of numbers. In many computers and other kinds of processors, adders are used not only in the arithmetic logic unit(s), but also in other parts of the processor, where they are used to calculate, table indices, addresses and similar operations.

Although adders can be constructed for many numerical representations, such as binary-coded decimal or excess-3 the most widely recognized adders work on binary numbers. In cases where two's complement or ones' complement is being used to represent negative numbers, it is trivial to modify an adder into an adder. Other signed number representations require a more complex adder.

The adder we are using here is a ripple carry adder. It is possible to create a logical circuit using multiple full adders to add N-bit numbers. Each full adder

inputs a C_{in} , which is the C_{out} of the previous adder. This kind of adder is called a ripple-carry adder [5], since each carry bit "ripples" to the next full adder. Note that the first (and only the first) full adder may be replaced by a half adder.

The ripple carry adder is implemented using full adder as the basic building block.

Fig.1. 4 Bit Ripple Carry Adders

The Fig.1 shows 4 bit ripple carry adder which is constructed with using 4 full adders. The input carry in the least significant position is 0. Each full adder receives the corresponding bits of A and B and the input carry and generate the sum bit for S and the output carry. The output carry in each position is the input carry of the next-higher-order position.

It can be inferred, that for N bit addition, the proposed ripple carry adder architecture uses only N reversible gates and produces only 3N garbage outputs. But, the ripple carry adder [4] using our proposed gate (PG) is the most optimized one.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

To generate the fast carry for intermediate stages by using kogge-stone adder. The carry propagation delay of adder is proportional to $\log_2(n)$ and the number of logic elements used is proportional to $n \log_2(n)$, where n is the number of bits used in addition. In this the carry select adder is implemented It mainly focus on to improve the performance of adder with reduced area, high speed and low power consumption. In digital adder circuits, the speed of addition is limited by the time required for a carry to propagate through the adder. Carry Select Adder (CSA)[6] is one among them and is used to solve the problem of carry propagation delay by independently generating multiple carries and then select a carry to generate the final sum.

IV. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

Kogge-Stone (KS) adder is a parallel prefix form Look ahead Adder [2]. Kogge-Stone adder can be represented as a parallel prefix graph consisting of carry operator nodes. The time required to generate carry signals in this prefix adder is proportional to $\log n$. It is the fastest adder with focus on design time and is the common choice for high performance adders in industry. The better performance of Kogge-Stone adder is because of its minimum logic depth and bounded fan-out. On the other side it occupies large silicon area.

The carry equations of KS adder are shown below. The carry propagation delay of the adder is proportional to $\log_2(n)$ and the number of logic elements used is proportional to $n \log_2(n)$, where n is the number of bits used in addition. The carry for different stages are

$$c_1 = g_0 + p_0.c_{in} \quad (1)$$

$$c_2 = (g_1 + p_1.g_0) + p_1.p_0.c_{in} \quad (2)$$

$$c_3 = (g_2 + p_2.g_1) + p_2.p_1.c_1 \quad (3)$$

$$c_4 = (g_3 + p_3.g_2) + p_3.p_2.(g_1 + p_1.g_0) + p_3.p_2.p_1.p_0.c_{in} \quad (4)$$

$$c_5 = (g_4 + p_4.g_3) + p_4.p_3.(g_2 + p_2.g_1) + p_4.p_3.p_2.p_1.c_1 \quad (5)$$

$$c_6 = (g_5 + p_5.g_4) + p_5.p_4.(g_3 + p_3.g_2) + p_5.p_4.p_3.p_2.c_2 \quad (6)$$

$$c_7 = (g_6 + p_6.g_5) + p_6.p_5.(g_4 + p_4.g_3) + p_6.p_5.p_4.p_3.c_3 \quad (7)$$

$$c_8 = (g_7 + p_7.g_6) + p_7.p_6.(g_5 + p_5.g_4) + \{p_7.p_6.p_5.p_4 [(g_3 + p_3.g_2) + p_3.p_2.(g_1 + p_1.g_0)]\} + p_7.p_6.p_5.p_4.p_3.p_2.p_1.p_0.c_{in} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 2. 4 Bit Kogge Stone Adder.

Fig. 2 shows the 4 bit implementation of KS adder. Implementation uses 31 two input logic elements and has 8 units delay. For delay calculation XOR is considered to have two units delay and all the other elements have single unit delay.

Carry input for the intermediate stages can be realized using Kogge Stone approach and by doing so we can eliminate the carry propagation through multiplexers as in CSA. CSA has lesser area utilization compared to KS adder. Area utilization of CSA can still be reduced by realizing the $C_{in}=1$ adder from $C_{in}=0$ adder, instead of going for a separate adder. Two different such realizations are discussed in the next section.

V. KOGGE STONE CARRY SELECT ADDER

Fig. 3 shows the proposed method of implementation of CSA. Here instead of using simple Excess ladder, first zero finding logic is used.

Fig.3. Carry Select Adder with KS adder ($c_{in}=0$).

If $C_{in}=0$, logic will select the KS Adder output as the final output from LSB to MSB until it finds the first occurrence of a zero. The proposed adder uses lesser logic elements compared to CSA with MUX.

A) KS Adder The below analysis is the result of the KS ADDER in Fig.4 which the inputs are a, b and C_{in} . The output is s and C_{out} . The input is taken as $a=1111$ and $b=0101$ and the output we get is $s=0100$ and carry out $C_{out}=1$.

Fig. 4. KS Adder.

B) SA with 16 bit KS adder

Fig. 5. CSA with 16 bit KS Adder.

The above analysis is the result of the 4bit with KS CSA adder in which the inputs are 'a','b' and C_{in} and the output is 's' and carry out is C_{out} . The input is taken as $a=Fh'4$ and $b=6h'4$ and the output we get is $s=5h'4$ and the carry out $C_{out}=1$.

The above analysis is the result of the 16bit KS CSA adder in Fig.5 which the inputs are 'a' and 'b' and the output is S_{out} and carry out is C_{out} . The input is taken as $a=FFFF h'4$ and $b=0000 h'4$ and the output we get is $s=FFFF h'4$ and the carry out $C_{out}=0$.

ii) CSA Zero finder From Fig.6 the input is taken as $a=1111$ and $b=0000$ and the output we get is $S=0000$ and the carry out C_{out} .

Fig. 6. CSA Zero finder.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this, we have shown the design of carry select adder implemented with Kogge Stone tree using zero finding logic to realize the carry select adder. CSA without MUX performs better in terms of area. CSA without MUX performs slightly better compared to CSA with MUX when the area-delay product is taken. Power, delay and area are the constituent factors in VLSI design that limits the performance of any circuit. This work presents a simple approach to reduce the area, delay and power of CSA architecture. It is simple and efficient for VLSI hardware implementations. In this way, the transistor count in a16 bits carry select adder without MUX can be greatly reduced from 62 to 37, more over the power consumption can be reduced from 1.26mw to 0.37mw.

The above analysis is the result of the KS Adder in Fig.4 which the inputs area, b and C_{in} . The output is s and C_{out} . The input is taken as a=1111 and b=0101 and the output we get is s= 0100 and carry out C_{out} =1.

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Reduction of THD for Bridgeless CUK Rectifier Topology in PFC Applications

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ABSTRACT

Bridgeless CUK rectifier has been three different topologies by reducing the bridge connected at front of the conventional circuit. The three topologies have their own construction based on different parameters and also switches. In this paper, the type-3 topology has been designed with less number of switches. This circuit gives low total harmonic distortion (THD) and less conduction losses with high efficiency. Type-3 topology is designed in discontinuous conduction mode (DCM) with input 100V_{rms} volts, output voltage as 20.5 V for 220W. Simulation results show that the circuit has high efficiency and less THD.

Keywords: CUK converter, DCM (discontinuous conduction mode), power factor correction (PFC).

I. INTRODUCTION

Power electronic equipment which is used to reduce THD with active power factor corrections. In conventional applications i.e., for Diode Bridge rectifiers can operate in continuous mode. But in proposed systems, the bridgeless topologies are used for low switching losses and high efficiency applications.

There are different bridgeless rectifiers as Boost, Buck, Buck-Boost, Sepic and CUK rectifiers [1]-[3]. In conventional circuit the current flows through two rectifier bridge diodes for one switching cycle which the switch is ON and other two bridge diodes conducts in next switching cycle.

Fig. 1. Conventional CUK rectifier

Bridgeless power factor correction(BPFC) one of which is boost converter has disadvantage of output ground has high frequency voltage in negative ac line due to which effects system stability[4]-[6]. Sepic converter has disadvantage of having discontinuous output current which affects high current ripples. In maximum power supply efficiency, the research efforts have been done and designed the bridgeless topologies. In this paper bridgeless cuk rectifier is performed and compared it with conventional.

II. CONVENTIONAL CUK RECTIFIER

The circuit diagram of Cuk rectifier is shown in fig.1 consists of AC input voltage source, bridge rectifier with diodes (D_p & D_n), input inductor L_1 , controllable switch Q , energy transfer capacitor C_1 , diode D_o , filter inductor L_o , filter capacitor C_o and load resistance R .an important advantage of this topology is that continuous current is present at both the input and the output of the converter and it protect from inrush currents and low current ripples.

When the switch is on, the diode D_o is reverse biased and the capacitor C_1 is discharged through the switch. With the switch is OF state, the diode conducts and

current flows through inductor L1 and L2, whereas capacitor C1 is charged by the inductor L1 current. The DC transfer function for the buck, boost and cuk converters converts DC-DC is continuous conduction mode are D , $1/(1-D)$, $-D/(1-D)$ respectively, where D is the duty cycle. The cuk DC-DC converter circuit can be synthesized by cascading boost and buck converters with minimum amount of components.

III. BRIDGELESS TOPOLOGIES OF CUK PFC RECTIFIER

The proposed topologies of bridgeless cuk rectifiers are shown in figure:2 .In this paper only type-3 topology is performed which the two DC-DC converters are connected for each half cycle i.e. $T/2$ period.

a) Type-1

b) Type-2

c) Type-3

Fig. 2. Topologies of bridgeless CUK rectifier.

IV. OPERATION OF TYPE-3 TOPOLOGY

The type-3 bridgeless CUK rectifier is performed in positive and negative switching cycles for which each of $T/2$ time period. Each half cycle of the circuit is operated in three stages based on the current flow and conduction of parameters.figure:3(a) shows the equivalent circuit for positive half cycle. In circuit switch Q1 is connected with the first CUK rectifier and switch Q2 to the second CUK rectifier. Four inductors are connected L1, L2, Lo1 and Lo2 which L1 and l2 are the inductors connected at load side, C1 and C2 are the capacitors which charges and discharges during the operation. Co is the filter capacitor which is used to reduce the current ripples and a load resistance is connected.

During positive half cycle, the first DC-DC link circuit will conduct i.e. the current path is shown as L1-Q1-C1-Lo1-Do1 which the current passes through diode Dp to the input. During negative half cycle, the second DC-DC link circuit will conduct i.e. the current path is L2-Q2-C2-Lo2-Do2 which current flows through diode Dn to the input.

a) Positive half line period

Fig. 3. equivalent circuits of positive and negative half line period.

The voltages at the capacitor can be calculated by input and output voltage given as:

$$v_{C_1}(t) = \begin{cases} v_{ac}(t) + V_o, & 0 \leq t \leq \frac{T}{2} \\ V_o, & \frac{T}{2} \leq t \leq T \end{cases}$$

There are four different modes of operating stages which the current flow.

STAGE-1: SWITCH Q1 IS ON

Fig. 4 a) Switch (Q1) is ON

From figure: 4 a) the mode of operation takes place when switch Q1 is ON and the parameters conduct are L1, L2, Dp, L01 and L02. From time period to-t1 the current passes through L1-Q1-Dp which forms a loop current and other loop as Q1-R&C0-L01-C1-Q1.the output diodes D01 and D02 are reverse biased by reverse voltage which less than Vac and Vo. the current across inductors L1 and L01 increases linearly with decrease in current at C1. The current in switch Q1 increases and voltage becomes zero.

STAGE-2: SWITCH Q1 IS OFF

Fig. 4. b) Switch (Q1) is OFF

In this stage, the switch Q1 if OFF and diode D01 get forward biased. From time period t1-t2, the voltage across D01 is zero and voltage across Q1 is Vac+V0 which the current across C1 decreases. Therefore current across D01 totally a discharge i.e. becomes zero. The current paths are shown as L1-C1-D01-Dp and other current is D01-R&C0-L01-D01 as shown in fig: 4 b).

STAGE-3: SWITCH Q2 IS ON

During this interval, only diode Dp conducts to provide a path for iL1.the current paths will provide two loop currents which as show AC(-ve)- L2-C2-D01-Dp-AC(+ve).

a) Switch (Q2) is ON

STAGE-4: SWITCH Q2 IS OFF

The type-3 converter of fig: 2 (c) is simulated with input voltage 100Vrms for the switching frequency $f_s=50$ kHz. The circuit components used in the Simulink is the same as table. 1.

Fig. 8 shows the simulation outputs for the type-3 topology CUK rectifier. Fig. 8 a) shows pulse generated for the switches Q_1 and Q_2 of switching frequency 50 kHz. Fig. 8 b) shows input current in phase with input voltage. Fig. 8 c) shows the current through the inductors L_1 and L_2 .

b) Switch (Q_2) is OFF

Fig. 4. Operating stages over one time period T_s for positive half cycle.

The capacitor C_1 is being charged by the inductor current IL_1 . This period ends when Q_1 is turned ON. These stages can be conduct in DCM which the theoretical waveforms can be given in figure 5.

The diode D_p continuously conducts through the entire switching period, the average voltage across C_2 is equal to the output voltage V_o .

The current through L_2 during the positive half cycle of the input voltage is equal to the negative current through the body diode of Q_2 .

table: 1 Component required in simulation.

Active switches Q_1 and Q_2	$R_{DS-ON}=29m\Omega$
Input inductors L_1 and L_2	1mH
Output inductors L_{o1} and L_{o2}	22 μ H
Capacitors C_1 and C_2	1 μ F
Filter capacitors C_o	12000 μ F
Output diodes D_{o1} and D_{o2}	$V_F=0.9v$
Input diodes D_p and D_n	$V_F=0.7v$

V. SIMULATED CIRCUIT FOR TYPE-3 PFC CUK RECTIFIER

Fig. 8d) shows currents through diodes D_p and D_n . Fig. 8e) shows current across the switches Q_1 and Q_2 . Fig. 8 f) shows the voltage across output diodes C_1 and C_2 . Fig. 8 g) shows the current through diodes D_{o1} and D_{o2} . Fig. 8 h) shows current through inductors L_{o1} and L_{o2} . Fig. 8 i) shows the output voltage at the load resistance of 5.5ohms. Fig. 8 j) shows the current at output at load resistance of 5.5 ohms

Table. 2 variation of THD.

Resistance(ohms)	THD%
5.5	32
4	26
3	20
2	14
1	9

VI. SIMULATION OUTPUTS OF TYPE-3 TOPOLOGY

a) Designed pulses of switching frequency 50 kHz

b) Input current in phase with the voltage with reduction of harmonics.

b) Inductor currents through L1 and L2

c) Diode currents Dp and Dn

d) Current through switches Q1 and Q2

e) Voltage at the capacitors C1 and C2

g) currents at output diodes Do1 and Do2

h) Currents at output inductors Lo1 and Lo2

i) Voltage at output at resistance of 5.5Ω

j) Current across output of load resistance 5.5Ω

Fig. 8. Simulated output of type-3 topology for input voltage 100V_{rms}, with load resistance of 5.5ohms output voltage 48V and power<300w.

Fig. 9. FFT analyses for input voltage 100Vrms

Fig. 10. FFT analyses for input current

Fig. 9 and 10 show the FFT analyses for input voltage and current.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

The bridgeless CUK rectifier type-3 topology is performed in this paper. Designing and simulated results are performed with low THD and high efficiency of < 300w power. Due to the low conduction and switching losses the efficiency can be improved more and the THD can be reduced for variation of load resistance.

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Fig. 1. Simulation Diagram of Type-3

Optimal Multi Antenna Spectrum Sensing Technique For Cognitive Radio

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we consider the primary user detection problem in cognitive radio systems by using multi antenna at the cognitive radio receiver. An optimal square law combiner multi antenna based spectrum sensing technique is proposed using the multitaper spectrum estimation method. The multitaper spectrum estimation method (MTM) produces single spectrum estimate with minimum spectral leakage and variance using an orthonormal family of tapers, the Discrete Prolate Slepian Sequences (DPSS). An energy detector (ED), which is simple, but has a poor performance at a low signal to noise ratio (SNR).

Keywords: Cognitive radio, spectrum sensing, multi taper spectrum estimation method, multi antenna spectrum sensing.ror.

I. INTRODUCTION

Radio Spectrum refers to the existing, natural medium that is used in different wireless communication systems and services: mobile, fixed, satellite-based, and low-power device communications systems (ultra wideband, sensors etc.)[1]. Due to increase in wireless technologies, there is a problem of spectrum scarcity. Cognitive radio (CR) is a new wireless communication technology that assigns a spectrum dynamically to the secondary users when the primary users are not using licensed spectrum.

There are different types of spectrum sensing techniques are there like Matched filter, Energy detector, cyclostationary, multi taper method. Matched filter [2] and cyclostationary are classified as high formance spectrum sensing techniques but they require every primary user transmitted signal i.e which requires primary user information. The disadvantage in the cyclostationary detection [3] is which requires cyclic frequencies of the primary user and also it takes long sensing time. Similarly the practical implementation of Energy detector is easy but gives very poor performance at low signal to noise ratio (SNR).

II. IMPORTANCE OF MTM METHOD FOR APECTRUM SENSING IN COGNITIVE RADIO NETWORK

Multitaper spectrum estimation method (MTM) was proposed in 1982 by Thomson [4]. MTM uses an optimal bank of band pass filters (known as tapers or windows). These orthonormal tapers are called Discrete Prolate Slepian Sequences (DPSS) [6]. MTM produces a single spectrum estimate with minimum spectral leakage and good variance. The spectrum estimation in MTM is an approximation of the optimal estimate; the maximum likelihood (ML), One advantage for MTM compared to ML is the fact that it has lower computation complexity. Since the first development of MTM in 1982, this advanced method has been widely used in many applications. In addition to the power spectrum estimation in signal processing and communications applications, MTM is used in neurosciences, geophysics and sonar.

III. THE IMPORTANCE OF USAGE OF MULTI ANTENNA BASED SPECTRUM SENSING IN CR SYSTEMS

In order to improve the spatial diversity, classical wireless communications use multi antenna at transmitter (Tx) or receiver (Rx) or both. Such

diversity improvement increases the system data rate and capacity. The reason behind this is that as the distance between antennas is chosen properly there will be a high probability of receiving independent fading through these different antennas [9]. Therefore, the fading effects will be mitigated.

IV. ENERGY DETECTOR

The probability of detection P_d is defined as is the probability that the CR detector decides correctly the presence of the PR's signal. Therefore, this type of probability is related to the $P(D; H_1)$ which represents the PR's signal plus noise

$$P_d = P_r \{D > \gamma / H_1\} = \int_{\gamma}^{\infty} P(D; H_1) dt \quad (1)$$

where P_r represents the probability .It is clear that p_d is the integration over $P(D; H_1)$ from the threshold γ to infinity. Since the $P(D; H_1)$ is assumed as Gaussian distribution; P_d can be defined finally as follows[5]

$$P_d = Q\left(\frac{\gamma - E[p(D; / H_1)]}{\sqrt{\text{VAR}[P(D; H_1)]}}\right) \quad (2)$$

where E and Var, are the mean and variance of the given distribution respectively. The term $Q(\xi)$ is the complementary cumulative distribution function,

$$Q(\xi) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{\xi}^{\infty} e^{-\frac{t^2}{2}} dt \quad (3)$$

The probability of false alarm, P_f is defined as the probability that the CR detector decides by mistake the presence of the PR's signal .Therefore, this type of probability is related to the , $P(D; H_0)$ which represents the noise only.

$$P_f = P_r \{D > \gamma / H_0\} = \int_{\gamma}^{\infty} P(D; H_0) dt \quad (4)$$

In this case, it is clear that the P_f is the integration over $P(D; H_0)$ from the threshold γ to infinity[5]

$$P_f = Q\left(\frac{\gamma - E[p(D; / H_0)]}{\sqrt{\text{VAR}[P(D; H_0)]}}\right) \quad (5)$$

where E and Var, are the mean and variance of the given distribution respectively.

V. MULTI TAPER SPECTRUM ESTIMATION METHOD

some of the advantages of multi taper estimation method are

1. MTM is an energy based spectrum sensing technique
2. MTM is a wideband spectrum sensing technique
3. MTM does not need any prior information about the PR's signal (i.e., non coherent nor partial coherent).
4. MTM needs to know the noise variance to control the threshold.
5. MTM minimizes the spectral leakage outside the band and improves the variance of estimate.

A general procedure for multi taper spectrum estimation consists of four steps. First, choose a time-bandwidth product $C0 = NW$ where N is the sample size for estimation, and W is the bandwidth normalized by the sample rate. The choice of parameter C0 is a trade-off between spectral resolution and variance. Typically, $3 \leq C0 \leq 6$, and we use $K = 2C0 - 1$ data tapers to perform the estimation for the reason that will be given below. Second, compute the data tapers, i.e., Slepian sequences.

Denote the k th data taper in vector form by w_k . It can be calculated by the following Eigen equation

$$KW_k = \lambda W_k \quad (6)$$

where the (i, j) th entry of Toeplitz matrix K is defined by

$$K_{i,j} = \frac{\sin 2\pi w(i-j)}{\pi(i-j)} \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N \quad (7)$$

The Eigen values λ_k range between 0 and unity, and are organized in an descending order such that $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots, \lambda_N$. The first

$K \approx [2NW]$ of them are dominated, close to unity, whereas the rest are negligible. Moreover, the tapers of lower order have much stronger energy-concentration capability than their high-order counterparts, suggesting that it suffices to use the first k tapers for spectral estimation. Third, the corresponding eigenspectra are defined by Fourier transform of the tapered (i.e., windowed) data sequences, resulting in

$$Y_k(f) = \sum_{n=1}^N w_k(n) x(n) e^{-j2\pi fn} \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k-1 \quad (8)$$

as a function of frequency f . Here, $w_k(n)$ signifies the n th entry of w_k . Given a finite sample-size constraint, the energy distribution of each eigenspectrum falls between the bandwidth from $f -W$ to $f +W$, due to energy-concentration property of Slepian sequences. Finally, we combine the Eigen spectra to form a single spectrum estimate,

$$s^{\wedge}(f) = \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \alpha_k |Y_k(f)|^2 \quad (9)$$

where the weighting factor $\alpha_k = \lambda_k / (\lambda_0 + \lambda_1 + \dots + \lambda_{K-1})$ is used to account for the relative importance of the Eigen spectrum of concern.

The received PR signal, at the CR receiver, is sampled to generate a finite discrete time samples series $\{x_{t,m}; t = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N-1, m = 1, 2, \dots, M\}$, where m denotes the antenna number and t is the time index. The discrete time samples are dot multiplied with different tapers $v_{t,k}(N, W)$ (Tapers are DPSS).

The associated Eigen value of the k^{th} taper is $\lambda_k(N, W)$. The product is applied to a Fourier transform to compute the energy concentrated in the bandwidth $(-W, W)$ centred at frequency, f . The half time bandwidth product is NW . The total number of generated tapers is $2NW$.

The binary hypothesis test for CR spectrum sensing at the l^{th} time, and using the m^{th} antenna branch is given by

$$H_0 : x_{t,m}(l) = w_{t,m}(l) \quad (10)$$

$$H_1 : x_{t,m}(l) = s_t(l) + w_{t,m}(l)$$

where $l=0, 1, 2, \dots, L-1$ OFDM block's index, and $x_{t,m}(l), w_{t,m}(l)$ and $s_t(l)$ denote the CR received, noise at the branch m and PR's transmitted samples.

The transmitted PR signal is distorted by the zero mean AWGN, $w_{t,m}(l) \approx N(0, \sigma_w^2)$ at the output from the different antenna branches, which are independent and with identical variance. For K orthonormal tapers used in the MTM, there will be K different Eigen spectra produced from each antenna defined as [6]

$$Y_{k,m}(f_i) = \sum_{t=0}^{N-1} v_{(t,k)}(N, W)(x_{t,m}(l))e^{-j2\pi f_i t} \quad (11)$$

where $f_i = 0, \frac{1}{N}, \frac{2}{N}, \frac{3}{N}, \dots, \frac{N-1}{N}$ are the normalized frequency bins.

The power spectrum estimate given by [4]

$$S_{MTM}^m(f_i) = \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \lambda_k(N, W) |Y_{k,m}(f_i)|^2}{\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \lambda_k(N, W)} \quad (12)$$

The energy detector, when the samples are taken at uniform time spacing, gives the power spectrum density estimation[7]

$$S_{ED}^m(f_i) = \left| \sum_{t=0}^{N-1} x_{t,m}(l) e^{-j2\pi f_i t} \right|^2 \quad (13)$$

A) Decision statics for the MTM and ED

The decision statistic over L using MTM is defined for the m^{th} antenna as

$$DEC_{MTM}^m(f_i) = \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \lambda_k(N, W) \left| \sum_{t=0}^{N-1} v_{t,k}(N, W) x_{t,m}(l) e^{-j2\pi f_i t} \right|^2}{\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \lambda_k(N, W)} \quad (13)$$

The decision statistic over L using ED is defined for the m^{th} antenna as

$$DEC_{ED}^m(f_i) = \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} \left| \sum_{t=0}^{N-1} x_{t,m}(l) e^{-j2\pi f_i t} \right|^2 \quad (14)$$

B) Mean and Variance of MTM and ED using Single Antenna

For single antenna MTM-based spectrum sensing, and according to the central limit theorem, if the number of samples L , is large, the decision statistic, $DEC_{MTM}^m(f_i)$ is asymptotically normally distributed with mean[8]

$$E[DEC_{MTM}^m(f_i)] = \begin{cases} LK\sigma_w^2 & H_0 \\ LK(E_s + \sigma_w^2) & H_1 \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

and variance (VAR)

$$VAR(DEC_{MTM}^m(f_i)) = \begin{cases} 2LC^2\lambda_2\sigma_w^4 & H_0 \\ 2LC^2\lambda_2\sigma_w^2(\sigma_w^2 + 2E_s) & H_1 \end{cases} \quad (16.1)$$

$$c = E \left[\frac{1}{\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \lambda_k(N, W)} \right] = \frac{1}{\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \lambda_k(N, W)} \quad (17)$$

The decision statistic, for the Energy Detector $DEC_{ED}^m(f_i)$ is asymptotically normally distributed with mean[9] (18)

and variance (VAR)

$$VAR(DEC_{ED}^m(f_i)) = \begin{cases} 2L\sigma_w^4 & H_0 \\ 2L\sigma_w^2(\sigma_w^2 + 2E_s) & H_1 \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

C) Detection and False Alarm probabilities

For a normally distributed decision statistic, $DEC(f_i)$ the probabilities of detection $P_d(f_i)$ and false alarm, $P_f(f_i)$ are defined as

$$P_d(f_i) = P(DEC(f_i) > \gamma / H_1) = Q\left(\frac{\gamma - E(DEC(f_i) / H_1)}{\sqrt{VAR(DEC(f_i) / H_1)}}\right) \quad (20)$$

$$P_f(f_i) = P(DEC(f_i) > \gamma / H_0) = Q\left(\frac{\gamma - E(DEC(f_i) / H_0)}{\sqrt{VAR(DEC(f_i) / H_0)}}\right) \quad (21)$$

The probability of miss detection $P_{mi}(f_i)$ is defined as

$$P_{mi}(f_i) = P(DEC(f_i) < \gamma / H_1) = 1 - Q\left(\frac{\gamma - E(DEC(f_i) / H_1)}{\sqrt{VAR(DEC(f_i) / H_1)}}\right) \quad (22)$$

The term $Q(\xi)$ is the complementary cumulative distribution function $Q(\xi) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{\xi}^{\infty} e^{-\frac{t^2}{2}} dt$ and γ represents the chosen threshold.

Thus, the different probabilities of MTM using single antenna can be redefined as [8]

$$P_d^{MTM}(f_i) = Q\left(\frac{\gamma - LK(E_s + \sigma_w^2)}{\sqrt{2LC^2\lambda_\Sigma\sigma_w^2(\sigma_w^2 + 2E_s)}}\right) \quad (23)$$

$$E[DEC_{ED}^m(f_i)] = \begin{cases} L\sigma_w^2 & H_0 \\ L(E_s + \sigma_w^2) & H_1 \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

$$P_f^{MTM}(f_i) = Q\left(\frac{\gamma - LK\sigma_w^2}{\sqrt{2LC^2\lambda_\Sigma\sigma_w^4}}\right) \quad (25)$$

$$P_{mi}^{MTM}(f_i) = 1 - Q\left(\frac{\gamma - LK(E_s + \sigma_w^2)}{\sqrt{2LC^2\lambda_\Sigma\sigma_w^2(\sigma_w^2 + 2E_s)}}\right) \quad (26)$$

The number of samples required by MTM using single antenna (L^{MTM}) can be written as [8]

$$L^{MTM} = \left(\frac{a^{MTM} - b^{MTM}}{KE_s}\right)^2 \quad (27)$$

where a and b are

$$a^{MTM} = \sqrt{2LC^2\lambda_\Sigma\sigma_w^4} Q^{-1}(P_f^{MTM}(f_i)) \text{ and}$$

$$E[DEC_{MTM-SLC}(f_i)] = \begin{cases} MLK\sigma_w^2 & H_0 \\ MLK(E_s + \sigma_w^2) & H_1 \end{cases}$$

$$b^{MTM} = \sqrt{2LC^2\lambda_\Sigma\sigma_w^2(\sigma_w^2 + 2E_s)} Q^{-1}(P_d^{MTM}(f_i))$$

$$E[DEC_{ED-SLC}(f_i)] = \begin{cases} ML\sigma_w^2 & H_0 \\ ML(E_s + \sigma_w^2) & H_1 \end{cases}$$

D) Mean and Variance of MTM and ED using M Antennas

The decision statistics for square law combining using M antennas for both techniques MTM, and ED respectively as follow [12]

$$DEC_{MTM-SLC}(f_i) = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} \frac{\left| \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \lambda_k(N,W) \sum_{t=0}^{N-1} y_{t,k}(N,W) x_{t,m}(l) e^{-j2\pi f_i t} \right|^2}{\sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \lambda_k(N,W)} \quad (28)$$

and

$$DEC_{ED-SLC}(f_i) = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} \left| \sum_{t=0}^{N-1} x_{t,m}(l) e^{-j2\pi f_i t} \right|^2 \quad (29)$$

The decision statistic using square law combining is a sum of identical and independent normally distributed M antennas decision statistics. Thus $DEC_{MTM-SLC}(f_i)$ the mean of the using M antennas [13] can be defined as (30) and the variance

$$VAR(DEC_{MTM-SLC}(f_i)) = \begin{cases} 2MLC^2\lambda_\Sigma\sigma_w^4 & H_0 \\ 2MLC^2\lambda_\Sigma\sigma_w^2(\sigma_w^2 + 2E_s) & H_1 \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

For the ED, the mean of the decision statistic, using square law combining through M antennas can be defined as (32)

VI. SIMULATION RESULTS

In our system each node of the cognitive radio (CR) network uses 64-FFT with sampling frequency 20MHz. The primary user (PR) transmitter uses 64-IFFT with symbol duration $T_s=0.05\mu s$, and transmits QPSK signal with normalized equal to 1 with each subcarrier. The multi antenna technique MTM-SLC, ED-SLC. In MTM techniques the used half-time and width product is $NW=4$, and the number of tapers $k=5$. In fig.1 and fig 2 consider the AWGN channel

with SNR=-10dB and 20 OFDM blocks (i.e L=20) used in sensing and the number of samples used is (L=20) X (N=64) =1280, which approximately corresponds to 64 μ s.

Fig. 1. Probability of detection Vs probability of false alarm using MTM and ED with M=4 Antennas at the Receiver.

Fig. 2. Signal to noise ratio (SNR) Vs probability of detection for M=4 Antennas at the Receiver.

Fig. 3. Signal to Noise ratio (SNR) Vs Number of samples (dB) for M=4 Antennas at the Receiver.

VII. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Here we consider the detection of primary user by taking MTM and ED detectors. Multiple antennas (M=4) used at the receiver side. Using multi antenna in MTM-SLC gives more improvement in performance compared to that for ED-SLC and also MTM method requires less number of samples to detect the primary user compared to the ED. The OR rule cooperation is used to cooperate the generated binary decisions from the individuals CR nodes at a

main CR-BS. Then the final decision is declared to the CR nodes.

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Where λ_{Σ} is

$$\lambda_{\Sigma} = \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \lambda_k^2(N, W) + 2\lambda_0(N, W)\lambda_1(N, W) + 2\lambda_0(N, W)\lambda_2(N, W) + \dots + 2\lambda_0(N, W)\lambda_{K-1}(N, W) + 2\lambda_1(N, W)\lambda_2(N, W) + \dots + 2\lambda_1(N, W)\lambda_{K-1}(N, W) + \dots + 2\lambda_{K-2}(N, W)\lambda_{K-1}(N, W)$$

(16.2)

PAPR Reduction in SFBC MIMO OFDM System Using ACE Scheme

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ABSTRACT

Increased data rates and reliability are the two key factors required to support emerging multimedia applications and new communications technologies. The two techniques used in high data rate transmission are orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) and multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) scheme. The OFDM is used to mitigate the problem of inter symbol interference (ISI) and provides good protection against co-channel interference and noise. MIMO system helps to reduce fading and can be used for decreasing bit error rate that is spatial diversity or to increase the data rate that is spatial multiplexing. The combination of MIMO and OFDM is MIMO OFDM system. MIMO-OFDM system converts frequency selective MIMO channel into multiple parallel flat fading channels. One of the major drawbacks of in MIMO-OFDM systems is that the transmitted signal exhibits a high PAPR when the input sequences are correlated. In this paper, ACE and AMS schemes have been used to reduce peak to average power ratio (PAPR) in multiple input multiple output orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (MIMO OFDM) system with space frequency block coding (SFBC). The ACE scheme reduces the computational complexity and when ACE scheme is used with quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM). Simulation and results show that the AMS scheme reduces PAPR more efficiently than the AMS scheme.

Keywords: ACE, MIMO, OFDM, PAPR, SFBC.

I. INTRODUCTION

The basic idea of multicarrier modulation is to divide the transmitted bit stream into many different sub streams and send these over many different sub channels. Typically the sub channels are orthogonal under ideal propagation conditions, in which case multicarrier modulation is often referred to as orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM). The data rate on each of the sub channels is much less than the total data rate, and the corresponding sub channel bandwidth is much less than the total system bandwidth. The number of sub streams is chosen to insure that each sub channel has a bandwidth less than the coherence bandwidth of the channel, so the sub channels experience relatively flat fading. Thus, the ISI on each sub channel is small.

Moreover, in the discrete implementation of OFDM, often called discrete multi tone (DMT), the ISI can be

completely eliminated through the use of a cyclic prefix. The sub channels in OFDM need not be contiguous, so a large continuous block of spectrum is not needed for high rate multicarrier communications. Recently, various algorithms of the PAPR reduction have been proposed for single-input single-output (SISO) OFDM systems in the literature, including clipping, nonlinear commanding transform, coding technique, selected mapping (SLM), go lay sequence and the weighting factor estimation Method. However, when these methods are employed directly to reduce the PAPR in MIMO-OFDM systems, it results in increasing of the complexity and redundancy with the increasing number of antennas.

Therefore, several new schemes have been proposed specially for MIMO-OFDM systems, such as the method of the poly-phase interleaving and inversion

(PII). The best advantage of both the ACE/AMS and PII schemes is that they could provide a good PAPR reduction without signal distortion. However, the computational complexity of the ACE/AMS and PII schemes is very high because they need to implement some extra inverse discrete Fourier transform (IDFT) operations and iterations of phase optimization. Obviously, the computational complexity of the scheme proposed in is reduced, which is at the cost of losing PAPR reduction.

Moreover, its optimal phase rotation vectors also need to be transmitted as side information to the receiver, resulting in loss of the data rate. In this paper, we propose partial transmit sequences (PTS) scheme to reduce the PAPR of MIMO-OFDM signals. For convenience and simplicity, the space time block coding (STBC) is employed in MIMO-OFDM systems in this paper. For the proposed ACE method, original data sequences at two antennas are partitioned into several pairs of sub blocks, and each pair of sub blocks multiplies by different factors to generate different pair of sub blocks.

Then, the obtained new sub blocks are combined to generate AMS, which keep the structure and the diversity capability of the SFBC. Finally, the pair of alternative sequences with the smallest PAPR is chosen to be transmitted. Obviously, the factors of the selected pair of sequences have to be transmitted as side information. However, if the factors are chosen particularly, the transformed pair of the constellation points corresponds to only one pair of original constellation points. As a result, the received pair of the constellation points could determine its corresponding original data without side information at the receiver. Simulation results show that the proposed ACE scheme could provide good PAPR reduction, and the ACE-SFBC method without side information could provide the same bit error rate (BER) performance as that of the AMS scheme with MIMO-OFDM with 4-QAM and 16-QAM, respectively.

II. PEAK-TO-AVERAGE POWER RATIO IN OFDM SYSTEM

It is defined as the large variation or ratio between the average signal power and the maximum or minimum signal power. Theoretically, large peaks in OFDM system can be expressed as Peak-to Average

Power Ratio (PAPR) and it is usually defined as

$$PAPR = \frac{P_{Peak}}{P_{Average}} = 10 \log_{10} \frac{\max [|x_n|^2]}{E|x[n]|^2}$$

where **P peak** represents peak output power, **P average** means average output power [E]. Denotes the expected value, represents the transmitted OFDM signals which are obtained by taking IFFT operation on modulated input symbols. Mathematical, is expressed as

$$x_n = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} X_k W_N^{nk} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

For an OFDM system with sub-carriers, the peak power of received signals is N times the average power when phase values are the same. The PAPR of baseband signal [2] will reach its theoretical maximum at PAPR (db) =10logN. Another commonly used parameter is the Crest Factor (CF), which is defined as the ratio between maximum amplitude of OFDM signal $x(t)$ and root-mean-square (RMS) of the waveform. In this MIMO OFDM system, SFBC codes are used as a channel coding technique to do error correction and detection and ACE/AMS scheme is employed to reduce PAPR. The input bits are given to modulator where modulation of input bits takes place using M-QAM complex constellation. The modulated signal is given by:

$$S_m(t) = A_m g(t) \cos(2\pi f_c t) - A_s g(t) \sin(2\pi f_c t) \dots(2)$$

A_m and A_s are information bearing signal amplitudes of quadrature carriers and $g(t)$ is the input-signal pulse. M-QAM modulated symbols are passed through the STBC encoder and complex matrix Z is generated such that symbols are coded through space and time. So, replicas of modulated symbols for block coding are sent through two transmit antennas and over two time slots.

The encoded sequence can be found by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Max}(z(n)) &= \text{sum}(\max(z(n))) \\ Z_{n_r} &= \text{real}(Z(n)) \\ Z_{n_i} &= \text{imaginary}(Z(n)) \dots(3) \end{aligned}$$

The encoded bits are given to the OFDM modulator where the bits are mapped with the orthogonal carriers. An inverse FFT is computed on each set of symbols, giving a set of complex time-domain samples.

$$z(n) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} Z(k) e^{j2\pi nk/N} \quad \dots\dots(4)$$

where $j = n = 0, 1, \dots (N-1)$. After OFDM modulation, ACE or AMS scheme is applied to reduce PAPR. Finally, the signal with minimum PAPR is transmitted through its respective antennas.

PAPR of MIMO-OFDM system is defined by

$$PAPR(z(n)) = \frac{\max\{|z(n)|^2\}}{E\{|z(n)|^2\}} \quad \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

where $E\{\cdot\}$ is the mathematical expectation.

Complementary cumulative density function (CCDF) for PAPR is given by:

$$CCDF(PAPR(z(n))) = P_r(PAPR(z(n)) > PAPR_o) \quad \dots\dots (6)$$

III. AMS SCHEME

The AMS scheme is after STBC encoder, the coded data is partitioned into sub blocks, and IFFT operation is performed on each sub block where the frequency domain signals are converted into time domain signals. Finally, AMS scheme is implemented, in which two inputs are given to the AMS block one input is from IFFT block and another input to AMS block is the conjugate of the output of the IFFT block.

Suppose the output of the IFFT block is $Y(m)$; $[m=0, 1, 2 \dots m-1]$, then the two inputs to the AMS block will be t_1 and t_2 where, $t_2=t_1^*$

AMS scheme will generate new sequences which are given by

$$\begin{aligned} T_1' &= [a(t_1) c]^{m+} [bt_2]^{m-} \\ T_2' &= [a(t_2) c]^{m-} [bt_1]^{m+} \quad \dots\dots\dots(7) \end{aligned}$$

where a^m and b^m are positive integers with $a^m \neq 0$, c^m and 1 and 2 respectively. Then the alternate transmitted signals are given by:

$$t_i = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} t_i^m \quad \dots\dots \quad \dots\dots(8)$$

where $i=1, 2, 3, \dots$. Finally, the signal with the lowest PAPR is chosen for transmission.

Table 1. PAPR results for AMS different QAM.

Different QAM		PAPR
Original OFDM	4-QAM	11.8db
	16-QAM	11.23db
4QAM	AMS M=2	9.8db
	AMS M=4	8.8db
16QAM	AMS M=2	10.2db
	AMS M=4	7.5db
64QAM	Without SFBC	10.25db
	With SFBC	6.25db

IV. AMS WITH SFBC SCHEME

Key idea of the proposed scheme is keeping the advantage of the SFBC structure to generate some AMSs via combining the signals at different transmit antennas. Specifically, when the proposed scheme is employed in SFBC MIMO OFDM systems with quadrature-amplitude modulation (QAM), For convenience and simplicity, the space-frequency block coding (SFBC) is employed in MIMO-OFDM systems in this project original data sequences at two antennas are partitioned into several pairs of sub blocks, and each pair of sub blocks multiplies by different factors to generate different pair of sub blocks.

V. ACE SCHEME

The Active Constellation Extension (ACE) is an attractive technique because of good PAPR reduction performance and no restriction to the number of subcarriers [13]. It can be said that ACE method is a modified method of AMS. ACE method works better than AMS method. The main advantage of this scheme is that there is no need to send any side information to the receiver of the system, when, differential modulation is applied in all sub blocks. In this scheme, the coming input bits are divided into smaller disjoint sub blocks. Input from each partitioned sub block converted from frequency domain to time domain by using N-point inverse fast Fourier transform (IFFT). The time domain sequences

are multiplied by rotating phase factors $Z = [Z_1, Z_2, Z_3 \dots Z_m]^T$, to minimize PAPR and then these sequences are then added to form the OFDM symbol for transmission.

The resulting time domain signal,

$$x'(z) = \sum_{m=1}^M z_m \cdot x_m$$

$$z_m = e^{j\phi_m}$$

Allowable phase factor,

X_m is the time domain sequence and ϕ_m can take the value between $(0, 2\pi)$. The main aim of this scheme is to design an optimal phase factor for each sub block set that minimizes the PAPR. Finally, the signal with the lowest PAPR is chosen for transmission.

VI. ACE WITH SFBC SCHEME

ACE Based are increased with a total transmit power constraint over additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) channel. Moreover, we derive the quantitative relations between PAPR reductions using SFBC (Space Frequency Block Coding). In order to eliminate the over head respective to side information concerning the sequence of pre-coders employed, we propose the use of pre-coded pilots.

Fig . PAPR Reduction on ACE with SFBC Using 256QAM.

Table 2. PAPR results for ACE scheme

256QAM	Without SFBC	Above 8db
	With SFBC	6.25db
128QAM	Without SFBC	Above 8db
	With SFBC	5.45db
64QAM	Without SFBC	Above 8db
	With SFBC	4.85db

Fig . PAPR Reduction on ACE with SFBC Using 128 QAM.

Fig . PAPR Reduction on ACE with SFBC Using 64 QAM.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we investigated an efficient PAPR reduction technique dedicated to MIMO-OFDM systems using SFBC codebook. The main feature of our proposed method is that it induces an embedded signalling through the advanced pre-coders codebook that leads to a powerful recovery of the transmitted signal and guarantees a very low failure decision rate. To further improve the decision process, we proposed an additional embedded signal that consists of a set of rotated and un-rotated QAM constellations and when Used in the decision process (using a hard decision deduced from a Max-Log-MAP decoding), it significantly improves the MIMO-OFDM system performances in terms of CCDF of the PAPR, SIER and BER. This decision criterion ensures a good decision performance when the absolute LLR value is greater than a certain threshold. But when it is close to zero (for very low SNR values), the decision can be biased. To overcome this issue, conceiving a soft decision process would be an appropriate solution: this is a research aspect that we are currently investigating.

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Multiuser Detection over Generalized-K Fading Channels with MRC Receive Diversity in Presence of Impulsive Noise

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ABSTRACT

In direct sequence-code division multiple accesses systems (DS-CDMA), the signals are transmitted over multipath channels that introduce fading and shadowing. Multipath fading and shadowing along with multiple access interference and inter-symbol interference degrades the system performance. Further, experimental results have confirmed the presence of impulsive noise in wireless mobile communication channels. Hence, this paper presents a technique for multiuser detection in DS-CDMA systems over generalized-K (GK) fading channels in presence of impulsive noise. An approximate closed-form expression for average probability of error of an M-decorrelator is derived, for the demodulation of binary phase shift keying (BPSK) signals transmitted over the channels with simultaneous presence of fading and shadowing. Maximal ratio combining (MRC) receive diversity is also incorporated to mitigate the effects of fading and shadowing. Performance of a new M-estimator based detector is also studied by evaluating error rate with the derived expression. Simulation results reveal that the proposed M-estimator based detector performs better in the presence of fading, shadowing and heavy-tailed impulsive noise.

Keywords: Diversity combining, fading channel; GK distribution; impulsive noise; multiuser detection; probability of error, shadowing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent research has explored the potential benefits of multiuser detection for code division multiple access (CDMA) communication systems with present multiple access interference (MAI) [1]. These optimal multiuser detectors have led to the developments of the various linear multiuser detectors with Gaussian noise though various experimental results have confirmed that many realistic channels are impulsive in nature [2], [3]. Lately, the problem of robust multiuser detection in non-Gaussian channels has been addressed in the literature [4], [5], [6], which were developed based on the Huber, Hampel, and a new M-estimator (modified Hampel), respectively. Since CDMA transmissions are frequently made over channels that exhibit fading, it is of interest to design receivers that take this fading behavior of the channel in to account [3]. Robust multiuser detection for

synchronous DS-CDMA system with maximal ratio combiner (MRC) receive diversity over Nakagami-m fading channels is presented in [7] by assuming that the modulation is binary PSK (BPSK). But, the simultaneous presence of multipath fading and shadowing leads to worsening the wireless channels [8]. Recently, the performance of M-decorrelator in simultaneous presence of fading and shadowing with impulsive noise is presented in [9]. Hence, in this paper, the problem of multiuser detection for DS-CDMA system over generalized-K (GK) fading channels with impulsive noise is considered. D-branch MRC receive diversity is incorporated to mitigate the effects of multipath fading.

DS-CDMA system over multipath fading channel in non-Gaussian impulsive noise environment is presented in Section II. Section III presents the GK

fading channel with MRC receive diversity. Influence function of the proposed M-estimator is presented in Section IV and an approximate closed-form expression for average probability of error of an M-decorrelator is also derived. Section V presents some simulation results. Section VI concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

An L-user CDMA system, where each user transmits information by modulating a signature sequence over a single-path Nakagami-m fading channel, is considered in this paper. The received signal over one symbol duration can be modeled as [3]

$$r(t) = \Re \left\{ \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{i=0}^{M-1} b_l(i) \alpha_l(t) e^{j\theta_l(t)} s_l(t - iT_s - \tau_l) \right\} + n(t) \quad (1)$$

where $\Re\{\cdot\}$ denotes the real part, M is the number of data symbols per user in the data frame of interest, T_s is the symbol interval, $\alpha_l(t)$ is the time-varying fading gain of the l^{th} user's channel, $\theta_l(t)$ is the time-varying phase of the l^{th} user's channel, $b_l(i)$ is the i^{th} bit of the l^{th} user, $s_l(t)$ is the normalized signaling waveform of the l^{th} user and $n(t)$ is assumed as a zero-mean complex non-Gaussian noise. It is assumed that the signaling constellation consists of non-orthogonal signals given by [3]

$$s_l(t) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{\frac{2}{T}} a_l(t) e^{j(\omega_c t + \theta_l)} & \text{for } t \in [0, T_s] \\ 0 & \text{for } t \notin [0, T_s] \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $j = \sqrt{-1}$, θ_l is the phase of the l^{th} user relative to some reference, ω_c is the common carrier frequency, and the spreading waveforms, $a_l(t)$, are of the form

$$a_l(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N a_n^l u_{T_c}^l(t - (n-1)T_c) \quad (3)$$

where $\{a_n^l\}_{n=1}^N$ is a signature sequence of +1s and -1s assigned to the l^{th} user, and $u_{T_c}^l(t)$ is a unit-amplitude pulse of duration T_c with $T_s = NT_c$. At the receiver, the received signal $r(t)$ is first filtered by a chip-matched filter and then sampled at the chip rate, $1/T_c$. The resulting discrete-time signal sample corresponding to the n^{th} chip of the i^{th} symbol is given by [3]

$$r_n(i) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{T_c}} \int_{iT_s + nT_c}^{iT_s + (n+1)T_c} r(t) e^{-j\omega_c t} dt, n = 1 \dots N. \quad (4)$$

For synchronous case (i.e., $\tau_1 = \tau_2 = \dots = \tau_l = 0$), assuming that the fading process for each user varies at a slower rate that the magnitude and phase can taken to be constant over the duration of a bit, (4) can be expressed in matrix notation as [3]

$$\underline{r}(i) = \underline{A}\underline{\theta}(i) + \underline{w}(i) \quad (5)$$

where

$$\underline{r}(i) \triangleq [r_1(i), \dots, r_N(i)]^T \quad (6)$$

$$\underline{w}(i) \triangleq [w_1(i), \dots, w_N(i)]^T \quad (7)$$

$$\underline{\theta}(i) \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} [b_1(i)g_1(i), \dots, b_L(i)g_L(i)]^T \quad (8)$$

with $w_n(i)$ is a sequence of independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) complex random variables whose in-phase and quadrature components are independent non-Gaussian random variables with probability density function (PDF) of this noise model has the form

$$f = (1 - \varepsilon)\mathcal{N}(0, \nu^2) + \varepsilon\mathcal{N}(0, \kappa\nu^2) \quad (9)$$

with $\nu > 0$, $0 \leq \varepsilon \leq 1$, and $\kappa \geq 1$. Here $\mathcal{N}(0, \nu^2)$ represents the nominal background noise and the $\mathcal{N}(0, \kappa\nu^2)$ represents an impulsive component, with ε representing the probability that impulses occur. It is assumed that the l^{th} user employs binary phase shift keying (BPSK) modulation to transmit the data bits $b_l \in [-1, 1]$ with equal probability and a symbol rate $1/T_s$.

III. GK FADING CHANNEL WITH MRC DIVERSITY

It is assumed that the signal of each user arrives at the receiver through an independent, single-path fading channel. For the shadowed fading channels, $\alpha_l(i)$ are i.i.d. random variables with GK distribution given by [8]

$$p_\alpha(\alpha_l) = \frac{2}{\Gamma(m)\Gamma(\mu)} \left(\sqrt{\frac{m\mu}{\Omega_0}} \right)^{m+\mu} \alpha_l^{\frac{m+\mu}{2}-1} K_{m-\mu} \left(2\sqrt{\frac{m\mu}{\Omega_0}} \alpha_l \right) \quad (10)$$

where, m is the Nakagami fading parameter that determines the severity of the fading, μ represents the shadowing levels, Ω_0 is the average SNR in a shadowed fading channel, $K_\xi(\cdot)$ is the modified Bessel function and $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the Gamma function [10].

Assuming that the fading is mitigated through D-branch MRC, the output of maximal ratio combiner can be written as [8, 11]

$$R = \sum_{j=1}^D \alpha_j \quad (11)$$

where α are i.i.d. GK distributed random variables each having a PDF of the form (10). The PDF of R, with multipath fading and shadowing from branch to branch are distinct, is given by [8]

$$P_R(r) = \frac{2}{\Gamma(m_m)\Gamma(\mu_m)} \left(\sqrt{\frac{m_m\mu_m}{\Omega_o}} \right)^{m_m+\mu_m} \times r^{\frac{m_m+\mu_m-1}{2}} \times K_{m_m-\mu_m} \left(2\sqrt{\frac{m_m\mu_m}{\Omega_o}} r \right) \quad (12)$$

where

$$m_m = Dm + (D-1) \left[\frac{-0.127-0.95m-0.0058\mu}{1+0.00124m+0.98\mu} \right] \quad (13)$$

and

$$\mu_m = D\mu. \quad (14)$$

Fig. 1. Influence functions of (a) the linear decorrelating detector, (b) Huber estimator, (c) Hampel estimator, and (d) the proposed estimator.

IV. MULTI TAPER SPECTRUM ESTIMATION METHOD

In this section, the proposed M-estimator is presented and the average probability of error is derived for a single-path shadowed fading channel.

A) M-estimator

An M-estimator is, a generalization of usual maximum likelihood estimates, used to estimate the unknown parameters $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_L$ (where $\theta=Ab$) by minimizing a sum of function $\rho(\cdot)$ of the residuals [4]

$$\hat{\theta} = \arg \min_{\theta \in \mathcal{R}^L} \sum_{j=1}^N \rho \left(r_j - \sum_{l=1}^L s_j^l \theta_l \right) \quad (15)$$

where ρ is a symmetric, positive-definite function with a unique minimum at zero, and is chosen to be less increasing than square and N is the processing gain. An influence function $\psi(\cdot) = \rho'(\cdot)$ is proposed (as shown in Fig. 1 along with other influence functions), such that it yields a solution that is not sensitive to outlying measurements, as [6]

$$\psi_{PRO}(x) = \begin{cases} x & \text{for } |x| \leq a \\ a \operatorname{sgn}(x) & \text{for } a < |x| \leq b \\ \frac{a}{b} x \exp\left(1 - \frac{x^2}{b^2}\right) & \text{for } |x| > b \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where the choice of the constants a and b depends on the robustness measures.

B) Average probability of error

The asymptotic probability of error for the class of decorrelating detectors, for large processing gain N , is given by [4]

$$P_e^l \equiv \Pr(\hat{\theta}_l < 0 | \theta_l > 0) = Q \left(\frac{A_l}{v \sqrt{[\mathbf{R}^{-1}]_{ll}}} \right) \quad (17)$$

where $Q(x)$ is the Gaussian Q-function [11],

$$v^2 = \frac{\int \psi^2(u) f(u) du}{\left[\int \psi'(u) f(u) du \right]^2} \quad (18)$$

and $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{S}^T \mathbf{S}$ with \mathbf{S} is an $N \times L$ matrix of columns \mathbf{a}_l . Average probability of error can be obtained by averaging the conditional probability of error (17) over the PDF, (12), of maximal ratio combiner output as

$$\overline{P_e^l} = F \cdot \int_0^\infty x^{\left(\frac{m_m+\mu_m-1}{2}\right)} Q \left(\frac{x}{v \sqrt{[\mathbf{R}^{-1}]_{ll}}} \right) \times K_{m_m-\mu_m} \left(2\sqrt{\frac{m_m\mu_m}{\Omega_o}} x \right) dx \quad (19)$$

where $F = \frac{2}{\Gamma(m_m)\Gamma(\mu_m)} \left(\sqrt{\frac{m_m\mu_m}{\Omega_o}} \right)^{m_m+\mu_m}$. Using the well known upper-bound approximation, called Chernoff bound, to $Q(x)$, given by

$$Q(x) \leq \frac{1}{2} e^{-x^2/2} \quad (20)$$

the integral of (19) can be expressed as

$$\int_0^{\infty} x^{\left(\frac{m_m + \mu_m - 1}{2}\right)} \exp\left(\frac{-x^2}{\nu^2 [\mathbf{R}^{-1}]_{11}}\right) \times K_{m_m - \mu_m} \left(2 \sqrt{\frac{m_m \mu_m}{\Omega_o}} x \right) dx \quad (21)$$

Now, by using [Eq. 6.631.3, 10] to evaluate the integral (21), the average probability of error can be derived as [9]

$$\overline{P_e^1} = F \cdot \frac{1}{2} \xi^{-0.5l} \beta^{-1} \Gamma\left(\frac{1+d+l}{2}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{1-d+l}{2}\right) \cdot \exp\left(\frac{\beta^2}{8\xi}\right) W_{-0.5l, d} \left(\frac{\beta^2}{4\xi}\right) \quad (22)$$

where $d = m_m - \mu_m$, $l = \frac{m_m + \mu_m}{2} - 1$, $\xi = \frac{1}{\nu^2 [\mathbf{R}^{-1}]_{11}}$

and $\beta = 2 \sqrt{\frac{m_m \mu_m}{\Omega_o}}$ and $W_{\lambda, \gamma}(\cdot)$ is the Whittaker function [9].

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, the performance of M-decorrelator is presented by computing (22) for different values of order of diversity. It is assumed that $m = 1.4$, $\mu = 2$ and $\Omega_o = 10$ dB in the simulations.

Performance of M-decorrelator with different influence functions is shown in Fig. 2, Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. In Fig. 2, the average probability of error versus the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) corresponding to the user 1 under perfect power control of a synchronous DS-CDMA system with six users ($L = 6$) and a processing gain, $N = 31$ is plotted for Gaussian noise ($\varepsilon = 0$). In Fig. 3, the average probability of error is plotted for moderate impulsive noise ($\varepsilon = 0.01$). Similarly, in Fig. 4, the average probability of error is plotted for highly impulsive noise ($\varepsilon = 0.1$). Simulation results show that the proposed M-estimator based detector performs well compared to linear multiuser detector, minimax detector with Huber and Hampel estimator based detectors.

Fig. 2. Average probability of error versus SNR for user 1 for linear multiuser detector (Least Squares), minimax detector with Huber, Hampel and proposed M-estimator in synchronous CDMA channel with impulse noise, $N = 31$, $\varepsilon = 0$.

Fig. 3. Average probability of error versus SNR for user 1 for linear multiuser detector (Least Squares), minimax detector with Huber, Hampel and proposed M-estimator in synchronous CDMA channel with impulse noise, $N = 31$, $\varepsilon = 0.01$.

Fig. 4. Average probability of error versus SNR for user 1 for linear multiuser detector (Least Squares), minimax detector with Huber, Hampel and proposed M-estimator in asynchronous CDMA channel with impulse noise, $N = 31$, $\varepsilon = 0.1$.

VI. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Multiuser detection for DS-CDMA systems over GK fading channels under impulsive noise environment is presented. An approximate closed-form expression for average probability of error of the M-decorrelator to detect BPSK signals is derived by incorporating MRC receive diversity. An M-estimator based multiuser detector is proposed and its performance is analyzed by computing average probability of error using the expression derived. Simulation results show that the proposed multiuser detector offers significant performance gain over the linear multiuser detector and the minimax decorrelating detector with Huber and Hampel M-estimators, in heavy-tailed impulsive noise.

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Control Through Bus Based Fault Monitoring and Diagnosis System Using CAN

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ABSTRACT

The vehicle bus data acquisition and fault diagnosis system, focusing on its lower computer system and the upper computer system is designed. This system is based on the widely used CAN bus technology, to extract the vehicle's status or fault information. When the vehicle breaks down, the status of vehicle will be sent as SMS to the control system using GSM technology. In automotive electronics, engine fault detect units, engine temperature sensors, air bag release-systems and battery low level detect system etc. are connected using CAN with bit rates up to 1 M bit/s.

Keywords: ARM7, CAN protocol, GSM technology, sensors.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the continuous development of industrial, automotive technology and electronics technology has also made great progress. The structure of vehicles becomes more complex increasing the degree of automation is increasing, and the networks of the body are also increasing in the major car manufactures. This system is based on the widely used CAN bus technology, to extract the vehicle's status or fault information. The increasing complexity of automotive electronic control system makes automotive fault diagnosis and maintenance work more difficult. In the way, we need more skilled technicians and more advanced device to detect and maintain fault. We are also using GSM technology for sending information of BUS status when fault is detected.

II. RELATED WORK

A) CAN

The Controller Area Network (the CAN bus) is a serial communications bus for real-time control applications; operates at data rates of up to 1

Megabits per second, and has excellent error detection and confinement capabilities. CAN was originally developed by the German company, Robert Bosch, for use in cars, to provide a cost-effective communications bus for in-car electronics and as alternative to expensive, cumbersome and unreliable wiring looms and connectors[1]. The car industry continues to use CAN for an increasing number of applications, but because of its proven reliability and robustness, CAN is now also being used in many other control applications. CAN or Controller Area Network is a robust industrial strength hardware and software protocol used to communicate between microcontrollers. It is very popular in modern automotive applications and is gaining popularity in industrial and home automation applications.

Data messages transmitted from any node on a CAN bus do not contain addresses of either the transmitting node, or of any intended receiving node. Instead, the content of the message (e.g. Revolution Per Minute, Hopper Full, X-ray Dosage,

etc.) is labeled by an identifier that is unique throughout the network [2] [3].

All other nodes on the network receive the message and each performs an acceptance test on the identifier to determine if the message, and thus its content, is relevant to that particular node. If the message is relevant, it will be processed; otherwise it is ignored. The unique identifier also determines the priority of the message.

The lower the numerical value of the identifier, the higher the priority. In situations where two or more nodes attempt to transmit at the same time, a non-destructive arbitration technique guarantees that messages are sent in order of priority and that no messages are lost. CAN use Non Return to Zero (NRZ) encoding (with bit-stuffing) for data communication on a differential two wire bus. The use of NRZ encoding ensures compact messages with a minimum number of transitions and high resilience to external disturbance. The two wire bus is usually a twisted pair (shielded or unshielded). Flat pair (telephone type) cable also performs well but generates more noise itself, and may be more susceptible to external sources of noise.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of CAN protocol.

Fig. 2. Implementation of CAN protocol.

CAN will operate in extremely harsh environments and the extensive error checking mechanisms ensure that any transmission errors are detected [4] [5]. There are two types of CAN implementations depending in the size of the identifier fields are, The Standard CAN protocol (version 2.0A), also now known as Base Frame Format, supports messages with 11 bit identifiers. The Extended CAN protocol (version 2.0B), also now known as Extended Frame Format, supports both 11 bit and 29 bit identifiers. Most 2.0A controllers transmit and receive only Standard format messages, although some (known as 2.0B passive) will receive Extended format messages - but then ignore them. 2.0B controllers can send and receive messages in both formats.

B) GSM MODEM

GSM stands for Global System for Mobile Communication. It's a globally accepted standard for digital cellular communication. GSM is the name of a standardization group established in 1982 to create a common European mobile telephone standard that would formulate specifications for a pan-European mobile cellular radio system operating at 900 MHz. The GSM modem basically consists:

- SIM card holder to hold the activated SIM card for sending and receiving SMS.
- 5V AC power supply header to which the 5V ac adapter is connected.
- Power led which gives the indication of modem status that is on or off.
- 9 pin female to which the GSM antenna is connected

Fig. 3. GSM Modem Block Diagram.

Through the mobile equipment the network messages are sent and received. These messages are sent to the terminal adapter which is nothing but a GSM data card. Now if there is some data to be sent

to the mobile equipment then the terminal equipment that is basically a computer or processor sends out AT commands to the terminal adapter which in turn sends the mobile equipment the required data. The GSM modem being a serial communication device is connected to the serial port or a serial device through a serial connector. The power input to the modem is given through a 9v ac adapter. The LED will indicate different status of the modem are OFF (Modem is Switched off), ON (Modem is connecting to the network), Flashing Slowly (Modem is in idle mode), Flashing rapidly (Modem is in communication mode).

Fig. 4. Architecture of GSM network.

III. SYSTEM IMPLIMENTATION

Figure5: Block diagram of the system

In the implementation of our prototype system, vehicle interior network structure can use topology bus network, all the electrical systems nodes inside

the bus vehicle are attached to the CAN bus through their own respective CAN communication module. Here we are using one slave and one master. CAN/SMS Wireless Gateway not only be used to organize and coordinate all the interior electrical systems nodes, but also can be used as internal and external communications data interface. It gathered up the information from all the interior electrical systems nodes sent to the remote monitoring service center computer via SMS wireless module.

This paper focuses on bus data acquisition and remote monitoring system based on CAN bus and SMS, which can be used to improve the efficiency of monitoring, to maintain the system security, to lower the maintenance costs as well as the operating expensed. With the development of the mobile technology, the design will be made better; the data transmission based on wireless communication will be used more widely. The communication network designed is able to stay stable in a long run in the experiment and meets the expected target. Here, Keil cross compiler will be used for building the applications. LPC2148 development board will be used to test the built application. Flash magic software is used to dump the .Hex file in to the Microcontroller.

IV.RESULTANALYSIS

Figure6: Transmitter section of the Hardware design

Figure7: Receiver section of the Hardware design
Fig6 shows the transmitter section of the hardware design. It includes dc motor, temperature sensor, battery low level detect sensor and impact detect sensor. When dc motor off it will shows the status as fault is occurred in lcd. When the temperature of engine is high it will show the status as temperature is high in lcd. When the battery of engine is low it will show the status as battery is low in lcd. When the impact of engine is detected it will show the status as impact is detected in lcd. All the process will be done with the help of CAN protocol. After getting this type of results we will controls the engine of the vehicle.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper is implemented successfully for a vehicle data Acquisition and Fault Diagnosis System using CAN protocol and GSM technology, where we can also access accurate data in heavy network load. This project can be extended further by using GPS technology, to know the location of the vehicle where it's breakdown.

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Resource Allocation Based on Channel State Information in OFDM Systems

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ABSTRACT

Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiplexing is a modulation scheme specifically designed to facilitate high-speed data transmission over frequency-selective fading channels. Resource allocation based on channel state information is known to be a very powerful method for improving the spectral efficiency of Orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing systems. In case of static channels, the optimal resource allocation for multiuser Orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing systems has been investigated. For time-varying channel, the error in channel state information due to channel variation is recognized as the main obstacle for achieving the full potential of resource allocation. Finally, a maximum likelihood receiver for Multiband Keying signals is studied, where multiband keying is a modulation scheme proposed for ultra wideband systems. The receiver structure and the associated maximum likelihood decision rule is derived through analysis. A suboptimal algorithm based on a depth-first tree search is introduced to significantly reduce the computational complexity of the receiver.

Keywords: Orthogonal frequency division multiplexing, multiband keying, Resource allocation

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless communications industry has been expanding dramatically in part due to great progress in the areas of digital signal processing, In recent years, in order to satisfy the increasing demand for higher data rates, much attention has been devoted to broadband wireless communication systems. Orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM) system has a property of transforming a broadband channel into multiple narrowband sub channels.

Additional advantages of the OFDM system include high spectral efficiency, simple transceiver design, flexibility in terms of link adaptation, and so on. In the OFDM system, the effect of channel on each OFDM symbol is characterized by a complex vector known as the channel frequency response (CFR) [1]. The received complex symbols in all sub channels experience attenuation and phase shift determined by the CFR. Hence, for the purpose of coherent

demodulation, CFR need to estimate at the receiver. For this reason, channel estimation has received a great deal of attention in OFDM systems.

A major drawback of the OFDM system over frequency-selective fading channels is the high probability of bit error rate (BER) due to the possible existence of “weak” subcarriers.

For the sake of reliable communication, an approach using forward error-control code and frequency and/or time interleaving may be employed, which results in the so-called “Coded-OFDM (C-OFDM)” system [2]. Among them is the emerging Ultra Wideband (UWB) technique, which is based on a principle totally different from that of the OFDM system. It suggests using extremely narrow pulse signals that have a period of up to several nanoseconds to modulate data symbols. UWB comes from the fact that an extremely narrow

pulse in the time domain corresponds to an ultra wide bandwidth in the frequency domain.

Fig. 1. The architecture of a typical OFDM system

Meanwhile, the transmit power has been dispersed into multiple (independent) components, and a RAKE receiver is needed to collect these components for better decision [3]. UWB system known as “Multiband Keying” is addressed, whose maximum likelihood (ML) receiver over AWGN channel is investigated.

II. OFDM SYSTEM OVER FREQUENCY-SELECTIVE FADING CHANNELS

As mentioned in [1], OFDM systems can be realized with low complexity using the discrete Fourier transform (DFT). The structure of a typical OFDM system is illustrated in Figure 1.1, where the shadowed blocks correspond to the processing of OFDM. In this system, the number of subcarriers is denoted by N and the sampling rate is fixed to be $1/TS$, where $TS = 1/(N\Delta f)$ and where Δf is the frequency offset between neighboring subcarriers. Let $\{S_0, k, \dots, S_{N-1}, k\}$ denote the complex symbols that are transmitted within the k^{th} OFDM block. Then the output of the IDFT module in Fig. 1 can be represented by

$$X_{m,k} = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} S_{n,k} \cdot e^{j2\pi \frac{mn}{N}}, \quad m = 0, 1, \dots, N-1 \quad (1)$$

Let $c(\tau; t)$ denote the equivalent lowpass impulse response of a time-varying, frequency-selective multipath fading channel. According to [4], $c(\tau; t)$ can be written as follows

$$c(\tau; t) = \sum_{i=0}^{I-1} \alpha_i e^{-j2\pi\{(f_c + f_{d,i})\tau_i - f_{d,i}t\}} \delta(\tau - \tau_i) \quad (2)$$

where I denotes the number of propagation paths, and τ_i , α_i , and $f_{d,i}$ are, respectively, the propagation delay, the attenuation factor and the Doppler frequency offset for the i^{th} path. Moreover, $\delta(\cdot)$ is the Dirac delta function, and f_c is the center carrier frequency. The received baseband signal is given by

$$\begin{aligned} y(t) &= \int_0^\infty c(\tau; t)x(t - \tau)d\tau + \zeta(t) \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{I-1} \tau_i(t)x(t - \tau_i) + \zeta(t) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2. Performance of OFDM systems with uniform bit and power allocation

The main drawback of this approach is its poor performance in terms of bit error probability under frequency-selective (“nonflat”) fading channels. Figure 2 highlights this problem by comparing the system’s bit error rate (BER) over a given non-flat fading channel with that of a flat fading channel. In this figure, QPSK modulation has been used for all subcarriers. Fig 2 illustrates an example of bit and power allocation scheme designed for the non-flat fading channel profile shown in Figure 2. In this case, the number of bits sent by each OFDM block is the same as that of Figure 2. The performance of this bit and power allocation scheme is compared with the that of the flat fading channel with uniform bit and power allocation, and the results are plotted in Figure 3. It can be seen by comparing performance curves in Figure 2 and Figure 3 that the OFDM system using resource allocation has a much higher spectral efficiency than the system without it.

Fig. 3. Example of bit and power allocation for a non-flat fading channel

III. COMPUTATIONALLY EFFICIENT RESOURCE ALLOCATION FOR MULTI-USER OFDM SYSTEMS

The optimal subcarrier, bit and power allocation is a challenging task and its complexity is prohibitive in practical communication systems [5, 7]. To avoid this difficulty a tractable approach is to divide this problem into two separate problems: first find the optimal allocation for subcarriers to users, next, given the assignment of subcarriers, find the optimal allocation of bit and transmit power for each user. While the first step exploits the multiuser diversity, the second step makes use of the frequency diversity for each user. The main difficulty with the algorithms proposed in these references is their high computational complexity. While these algorithms may be applicable in wire line applications where the CSI remains static for extended periods of time, they are not suitable for the wireless environment where, even in the case of slowly fading channels, the CSI needs to be updated (and the solution recalculated) after several OFDM blocks. a novel method for subcarrier, bit and power allocation. We also consider the problem in two steps: subcarrier allocation to all the users followed by bit and power allocation for each user. Our algorithm achieves a near optimal solution with considerably less computational complexity than the optimal solution.

IV. AN EFFICIENT ALGORITHM FOR BIT AND POWER ALLOCATION.

In this section we temporarily ignore the problem of subcarrier allocation and assume that all the subcarriers have been pre-allocated to users. As a result the total number of subcarriers and the associated channel frequency response will be fixed

for every user. The optimal bit and power allocation can now be solved for a single user. Thus in the rest of this section we drop the subscript k and use N to denote the total number of subcarriers assigned to the individual user of interest.

$$\min_{\{\beta_n\}} \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\sigma_V^2}{|H_n|^2} \cdot f(\beta_n, \epsilon) \quad (4)$$

Subjected to

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^N \beta_n &\geq R \\ \beta_n &\in \Omega, \forall n = 1, 2, \dots, N. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The above is a mixed integer programming (MIP) problem requiring an exhaustive search with high computational complexity. In [8] the authors proposed a greedy method to assign bits iteratively until the target data rate is reached. During each iteration one more bit is added by searching for the smallest additional power necessary to guarantee the target BER.

V. AN EFFICIENT SUBCARRIER ALLOCATION METHOD

As mentioned previously the optimal allocation of subcarriers requires the solution of the constrained optimization problem which is computationally prohibitive. To get around the complexity issue, the problem of subcarrier allocation may be studied without involving bit and/or power allocation. In [9] it is shown that if the constraint in above is removed, then the optimal subcarrier allocation is to assign each subcarrier to the user whose power gain is the largest in that subcarrier. This approach, however, is unfair as it penalizes users whose channel power gains are small.

$$\sum_{n=1}^N \rho_{n,k} \geq \left\lceil \frac{R_k}{b_L} \right\rceil \quad \forall k = 1, 2, \dots, K \quad (6)$$

It is clear that any subcarrier allocation method that satisfies must also satisfy In other words is a necessary condition so that the data rate requirement of all users is satisfied.

VI. PERFORMANCE OF THE ABPA ALGORITHM

1,000 independent realizations of CFR using a 9-path outdoor channel model were generated [4]. The power delay profile for the simulated channel model is exponentially decaying with the maximum excessive delay of $5\mu\text{s}$ [4]. Specifically, the delay of these 9 rays are randomly generated within the $5\mu\text{s}$ interval while their amplitudes undergo independent Rayleigh fading. The CFR is generated by taking N-point discrete Fourier transform (DFT) for the samples of channel impulse response, where the sampling rate is $N\Delta f = 2.56\text{MHz}$. The resulting total receive power for all the subcarriers is calculated from the algorithm for each CFR realization and then averaged over the 1,000 realizations to obtain $P_{\text{ave}}(\varepsilon, R)$. The average SNR is then calculated as

$$\bar{\nu} = 10 \log_{10} \frac{P_{\text{ave}}(\varepsilon, R)}{N\sigma_V^2} \quad (\text{dB}). \quad (7)$$

Two values of $R = 256$ and $R = 512$ were used. Figure 4 illustrates the simulation results where BER ε is plotted vs. the SNR ν . In this figure the performance of the proposed ABPA algorithm is compared with that of the greedy method in [8] which is labelled as "optimal". For comparison the results for the non-adaptive OFDM system, where bit and power allocation is identical for all subcarriers has also been plotted. From Figure 4 we can see that the performance of the proposed ABPA algorithm is almost the same as the optimal method of [8] and is at least 10dB better than the non-adaptive system for BER 10^{-3} . The complexity of our algorithm is, however; significantly lower than that of the optimal solution. The number of iterations required for the ABPA algorithm to terminate is less than 7 in most cases. The worst case we observed involved only 14 iterations.

Fig. 4. Performance of the ABPA algorithms

VII. PERFORMANCE OF THE SA ALGORITHM

We now consider a MU-OFDM system with $K = 5$ users. The CFR for these users are randomly selected from the aforementioned channel realizations. The target BER for all users are set to the same value ε . For various users the target data rates and the average channel power gain given by $P_n |H_{n,k}|^2$ can be different. We have simulated two cases whose configurations are given in Table 3.1. In both cases we compare three different subcarrier allocation schemes. One is the algorithm presented in [10] and it is denoted by "WSA". Another is our proposed subcarrier allocation algorithm which is referred to as "SA". The third is a rate proportional FDMA scheme which yields a fixed subcarrier allocation, and is denoted by "FSA" [6] Fig. 5 and 6 illustrate the simulation results for both cases where the power of white noise are assumed to be identical for all five mobile stations. The system SNR is calculated from equation by replacing $P_{\text{ave}}(\varepsilon, R)$ with the average transmit power of the BS.

It is observed that when the WSA algorithm is employed the difference between using UBA or ABPA is negligible although the latter yields a better performance. Moreover, the performance of the system using both SA and ABPA is close (within 1.5dB) to the "WSA+ABPA" case whose performance is nearly optimal [10]. It is clear that the complexity for the proposed SA algorithm along with the ABPA algorithm is much lower than the WSA method making it more favorable for the wireless OFDM systems.

Table 1: User and channel configurations for the MU-OFDM system

User (k)	Case 1		Case 2	
	R_k	Average Power Gain	R_k	Average Power Gain
1	100	0dB	24	0dB
2	100	0dB	24	+2dB
3	100	0dB	128	-4dB
4	100	0dB	128	+6dB
5	100	0dB	208	-8dB

Fig. 5. Performance of the Subcarrier Allocation algorithm (case 1).

Fig. 6. Performance of the Subcarrier Allocation algorithm (case 2).

VIII. ON THE BIT AND POWER ALLOCATION FOR OFDM SYSTEMS WITH TIME-VARYING CHANNELS

Adaptive modulation has been recognized as an effective technique for improving the performance of wide-band communication systems over frequency-selective fading channels. we focus on the problem of resource allocation based on the noisy and outdated knowledge of the CSI. An earlier study in [11] shows that the state of a frequency-flat fading channel can be reliably predicted from the outdated observations across a long range of time. This motivates the prediction of frequency selective channels for the OFDM system since, using OFDM, the wide-band channel is transformed into a number of flat-fading sub-channels. We adopt the idea of CSI prediction and propose to perform resource allocation based on the predicted CSI.

Fig. 7. Performance of channel prediction in terms of NMSE.

$$\text{NMSE}_{\hat{g}(k)} = 2[1 - \text{Re}(\rho(dT_B))] + E(\|e\|^2)/E(\|g\|^2) \quad (8)$$

The above equation shows that if the outdated channel estimate is used as a prediction of the current CSI, the associated NMSE is not only determined by the signal to noise ratio (SNR) of the channel estimation method, but also the autocorrelation function $\rho(\cdot)$. It turns out that in this case the effect of the channel autocorrelation function is more significant than that of the estimation error. The NMSEs calculated from above equation using these two correlation functions have been plotted with respect to $f_m dT_B$ in Figure 7, where the SNR in the CIR estimation, namely the value of $E(\|e\|^2)/E(\|g\|^2)$, has been fixed to be 25dB. Fig. 7 illustrates that, when a delayed version of the estimated CIR is used for future CIR prediction, a small delay may result in large errors in CIR prediction even in cases where the estimation error is at an acceptable level (SNR=25dB).

IX. MAXIMUM LIKELIHOOD RECEIVER FOR THE MULTIBAND KEYING SIGNALS IN AWGN CHANNEL

Ultra Wideband (UWB) communication is now receiving a great deal of attention from the research community. The FCC has allocated a band of several giga hertz (3.1GHz – 10.6GHz) for the prospective UWB systems. According to FCC, a signal is qualified to be a UWB signal when it occupies a -10dB bandwidth which exceeds 500MHz or 20% of its center frequency [12].

The block diagram of the optimal receiver is illustrated in Figure 8. For each of the P branches, the MPSK receivers output not only the estimated signal phases but also the corresponding correlation values.

Thus in the case of large signal to noise ratio (SNR), the symbol error probability can be approximated by [13] It can be shown that the Euclidean distance between any pair of MBK symbols which have different frequency sequences is no less than $2\sqrt{E_s}$ for any P and M.

$$P_e \approx \begin{cases} P(2P-1)Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{2E_s}{N_0}}\right), & M=2 \\ 2PQ\left[\sqrt{\frac{2E_s}{N_0}}\sin^2\left(\frac{\pi}{M}\right)\right], & M>2 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Fig. 8. Maximum Likelihood receiver block diagram. The performance of the optimal receiver for QPSK (M=4) & 4 carrier frequencies (P = 4) and BPSK (M=2) & 5 carrier frequencies (P = 5) is simulated. For larger values of P the simulation of the ML decision rule becomes excessively time consuming as a result of exhaustive search. Figure 9 shows the symbol error rate (SER) of the optimal ML decision rule vs E_b/N_0 for the two cases described above. In this figure we also plot the symbol error rate obtained from the approximations in above equation. In both cases the simulation results match the approximation quite well, especially for large E_b/N_0 . This result holds for other values of M and P as well.

Fig. 9. Performance of optimal receiver

X. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, optimal resource allocation for multiuser orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing systems has been investigated.

Simulation results are provided for OFDM system over frequency selective fading channels.

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Evaluation of Predicted Throughput in TDD- LTE Systems

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the downlink throughput evaluation of Time division duplex Long Term Evolution (TDD-LTE). The system efficiency is assumed to be equal to the Shannon boundary. Pilot tones etc. is taken from TDD-LTE. Furthermore the packet header is part of the calculated throughput as it is highly dependent on the specific network. A large number of connected terminals will give a higher header/payload ratio, and for this reason it is not calculated in this investigation. Calculations show that RLAN's deployed in this frequency band produces high interference cannot supply high capacity access to internet. Only the rural case is investigated, and the interference radius is limited to 150 kilometres (a BDA2GC maximal radius is in this paper assumed to be 90 kilometres). Results show the capacity for a 20 MHz LTE-TDD systems as function of signal to noise ratio (SNR).

Keywords: Throughput, TDD, LTE, RLAN, SNR and BDA2GC.

I. INTRODUCTION

To address this growing mobile broadband demand, the 3GPP standards body released the next technological step, Long Term Evolution (LTE). LTE is designed to substantially improve end-user throughputs, increase sector capacity and reduce user plane latency. It is a simple and flat network architecture that delivers a significantly improved user experience with full mobility, resulting in low operating costs for operators. LTE is the logical next step for over four billion subscribers on 3GPP networks. Already over 100 global operators are committed to deploying LTE and have commenced technical evaluation and trials. FDD LTE, which uses a paired spectrum, one for uplink and the other for downlink, is the traditional modulation used by 3GPP operators and gained an early lead in LTE deployments.

TDD-LTE uses a different approach, a single frequency sharing the channel between transmission and reception, spacing them apart by multiplexing

the two signals on a real time basis. While FDD transmissions require a guard band between the transmitter and receiver frequencies, TDD schemes require a guard time or guard interval between transmission and reception. The time must be sufficient to allow the signal travelling from remote transmitters to arrive before a transmission is started and the receiver inhibited.

Typically more data travels in the downlink direction of a cellular telecommunications system, suggesting that the capacity should be greater in the downlink direction. TDD-LTE systems make this possible by changing the number of time slots allocated to each direction. Often this is dynamically configurable, so it can be altered to match the demand. Another characteristic of TDD-LTE transmissions is the aspect of latency. Due to the time multiplexing between transmit and receive, there can be a small delay between the data being generated and it being actually transmitted.

II. CAPACITY ESTIMATIONS FOR BDA2GC BASED ON LTE

This paper tries to investigate what capacity and throughput a BDA2GC system based on LTE can achieve in a rural RLAN deployment scenario. The calculations are based on the Shannon bound with LTE specific corrections for effective frequency usage, overhead and pilot tones. Possible uplink/downlink configurations for a LTE-TDD system are summarized in Table 1.

Table. 1. LTE-TDD uplink/downlink configurations.

Uplink/downlink configuration	Downlink-to-Uplink Switch-point periodicity	Subframe number									
		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
0	5 ms	D	S	U	U	U	D	S	U	U	U
1	5 ms	D	S	U	U	D	D	S	U	U	D
2	5 ms	D	S	U	D	D	D	S	U	D	D
3	10 ms	D	S	U	U	U	D	D	D	D	D
4	10 ms	D	S	U	U	D	D	D	D	D	D
5	10ms	D	S	U	D	D	D	D	D	D	D
6	5 ms	D	S	U	U	U	D	S	U	U	U

where D means downlink, U means uplink and S is the switch between downlink and uplink and consists of three parts, DwPTS(downlink part), GP(guard period) and UpPTS(uplink part). The different DwPTS, GP and UpPTS configurations are in the normal case:

Table2. Normal LTE-TDD uplink/downlink configurations.

	DwPTS									
	12	11	10	9	3					
GP	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	9	10	
UpPTS	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	

The downlink part (DwPTS) can be 3, 9, 10, 11 or 12 symbols. Depending on the DwPTS value the guard period (GP) and the uplink can differ. Capacity estimations are based on different uplink/downlink configurations as well as different configurations of the special sub frame S in order to establish both a best case and a worst case configuration scenario.

A) The Shannon bound

The channel capacity is the tightest upper bound on the amount of information that can be reliably transmitted over a communications channel in a given scenario (bandwidth, noise and interference). For a SISO (single input, single output) system the Shannon bound is (in bits per Hertz). All equations are in logarithmic scale (dB)

$$SISO = \log_2 \left(1 + 10^{S/10 \times N} \right) \left[\frac{Bit}{Hz \times s} \right]$$

For multi antenna systems the theoretical increase in SNR is maximum = $N_{receive} \times N_{transmit}$ for none correlated paths. In figure 1 the Shannon bound for different antenna configurations are depicted. Perfect orthogonality is assumed.

Fig. 1. The Shannon bound from SISO up to 4x4x4 MIMO (4 streams).

B) Transport capacity of LTE

From a radio point of view, LTE is very close to the Shannon bound and in the following calculations LTE is assumed to have a channel capacity that is only limited by the Shannon bound. This slightly overestimates the LTE capacity but is accurate enough for this study.

C) Spectral efficiency

The spectral efficiency of a LTE system can be calculated as

$$E = \frac{BW}{Ch.BW}$$

Where BW is the bandwidth and Ch BW is the channel bandwidth. BW is calculated by multiplying the number of resource blocks with the subcarrier spacing and the number of subcarriers per resource block.

That is

$$\xi = \frac{NRB \times SCS \times RB}{ChBW}$$

For a 20 MHz (ChBW) LTE system:

NRB (Number of Resource Blocks) = 100

SCS (Sub Carrier Spacing) = 15×10^3

RB (Number of subcarriers per Resource Block)

Hence the spectral efficiency of a 20 MHz LTE system is 0.90.

D) Time domain structure of LTE

With normal prefix structure a LTE system transmits 14 OFDM symbols per sub frame. With extended prefix structure 12 OFDM symbols are transmitted in one sub frame. Each symbol is nominally (1/spectral efficiency). The efficiency in the time domain can be calculated as

$$D \text{ efficiency} = \frac{\text{Number of OFDM symbols per frame}}{\text{Length of subframe} \times \text{spectral efficiency}}$$

The length of a sub frame is 1 ms, the number of OFDM symbols are 14 or 12 depending on the structure (normal structure gives 12 OFDM symbols per sub frame). The spectral efficiency can be calculated as explained in the previous section.

For a LTE system with spectral efficiency of 0.9 that is transmitting 14 OFDM symbols each sub frame the TD efficiency is

$$D E = \frac{14 \times \frac{1}{15 \times 10^3}}{1 \times 10^{-3}} = 0.93$$

E) Pilot tones

During one slot (7 symbols, 0.5 ms) 4 reference symbols are transmitted in each resource block. This leads to a reduction of $4/(12 \times 7)$ for a SISO system. For MIMO systems the overhead is increased due to the fact that only one antenna can send a reference signal on each carrier at a specific time. This gives $4 \times 2 \times 2$ occupied slots and a reduction of $2 \times 2 \times 4/$

$(12 \times 7 \times 2)$ for a 2 MIMO system. A 4 MIMO system has a reduction of $(4 \times 2 + 2 \times 2) \times 4 / (12 \times 7 \times 4)$.

F) Control signaling overhead

In each sub frame the 1-3 first symbols are used for control signaling, since there is no mixing of control signaling and data in an OFDM symbol. The more users in a cell, the more control signaling are needed, for the BDA2GC system only 1 symbol for control signaling is assumed. This gives an available payload of $\frac{-1}{4}$.

G) Uplink/downlink configuration

If uplink/downlink configuration number 1 (in table 1) is used, 4 out of 10 sub frames are used for downlink. 2 sub frames are switch sub frames and 4 are used for uplink. In the switch sub frames 3-12 symbols can be used for downlink transmission. This gives a downlink efficiency of $((4 \times 14 + 2 \times 3) / (10 \times 14))$ to $(4 \times 14 + 2 \times 12) / (10 \times 14) = 44\%$ to 7% .

III. CAPACITY FOR A LTE SYSTEM AS A FUNCTION OF SNR

An LTE system (considered to be on the Shannon boundary) that is subject to the above reductions the result (as a function of Signal to Noise ratio) have a channel capacity that is depicted below, this capacity includes the payload header that needs to be removed before the "user data capacity" is calculated.

Fig. 3. Channel capacity for a 20 MHz LTE TDD with different uplink/downlink configurations that gives a downlink efficiency of 44 % and 57 %.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Long Term Evolution (LTE) is the next generation OFDMA-based technology of choice for most 3GPP. In this paper, we explored downlink throughput evaluation of Time division duplex Long Term Evolution (TDD-LTE). With the envisaged throughput and latency targets and its emphasis on simplicity, spectrum flexibility, uplink/downlink flexibility, added capacity, and lower cost per bit, TDD-LTE is destined to provide many benefits.

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A Statistical MIMO FSO Channel Model for the Analysis of Outage Probability versus Signal-to-Noise Ratio

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ABSTRACT

A novel statistical channel model for multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) free-space optical (FSO) communication systems impaired by atmospheric and misalignment fading is developed. A slow-fading channel model is considered and the outage probability is derived as a performance measure. The diversity gain defined as the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) exponent at high SNR is analyzed. Interestingly in the presence of misalignment fading the diversity gain depends only on the misalignment variance and is independent of the number of transmitters M and receivers N . Increasing the number of transmitters and receivers only results in a lower probability of outage for given SNR, however, the rate of change is unaffected. Contrary to this, the diversity gain of MIMO FSO systems in the presence of atmospheric fading and no misalignment is shown to be proportional to the number of transmitters and receivers, particularly the product M and N .

Keywords: LS, FSO, MIMO, SNR.

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of multiple antennas at the transmitter and receiver in wireless systems, popularly known as MIMO (multiple-input multiple-output technology, has rapidly gained in popularity over the past decade due to its powerful performance-enhancing capabilities. Communication in wireless channels is impaired predominantly by multi-path fading. Multi-path is the arrival of the transmitted signal at an intended receiver through differing angles and differing time delays and differing frequency (i.e., Doppler) shifts due to the scattering of electromagnetic waves in the environment. Consequently, the received signal power fluctuates in space (due to angle spread) and/or frequency (due to delay spread) and/or time (due to Doppler spread) through the random superposition of the impinging multi-path components. This random fluctuation in signal level, known as fading.

MIMO technology constitutes a breakthrough in wireless communication system design. The technology offers a number of benefits that help meet the challenges posed by both the impairments in the wireless channel as well as resource

constraints. In addition to the time and frequency dimensions that are exploited in conventional single-antenna (single-input single-output) wireless systems, the leverages of MIMO are realized by exploiting the spatial dimension (provided by the multiple antennas at the transmitter and the receiver).

The advantages of multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) systems have been widely acknowledged, to the extent that certain transmit diversity methods (i.e., Alamouti signaling) have been incorporated into wireless standards. Although transmit diversity is clearly advantageous on a cellular base station, it may not be practical for other scenarios. Specifically, due to size, cost, or hardware limitations, a wireless agent may not be able to support multiple transmit antennas.

1.1 BENEFITS OF MIMO ECHNOLOGY

The benefits of MIMO technology that help achieve such significant performance gains are array gain, spatial diversity gain, spatial multiplexing gain and

interference reduction. These gains are described in brief below.

➤ Array gain

Array gain is the increase in receive SNR that results from a coherent combining effect of the wireless signals at a receiver. The coherent combining may be realized through spatial processing at the receive antenna array and/or spatial pre-processing at the transmit antenna array. Array gain improves resistance to noise, thereby improving the coverage and the range of a wireless network.

➤ Spatial diversity gain

As mentioned earlier, the signal level at a receiver in a wireless system fluctuates or fades. Spatial diversity gain mitigates fading and is realized by providing the receiver with multiple (ideally independent) copies of the transmitted signal in space, frequency or time. With an increasing number of independent copies (the number of copies is often referred to as the diversity order), the probability that at least one of the copies is not experiencing a deep fade increases, thereby improving the quality and reliability of reception.

➤ Spatial multiplexing gain

MIMO systems offer a linear increase in data rate through spatial multiplexing, i.e., transmitting multiple, independent data streams within the bandwidth of operation. Under suitable channel conditions, such as rich scattering in the environment, the receiver can separate the data streams.

➤ Interference reduction and avoidance

Interference in wireless networks results from multiple users sharing time and frequency resources. Interference may be mitigated in MIMO systems by exploiting the spatial dimension to increase the separation between users. For instance, in the presence of interference, array gain increases the tolerance to noise as well as the interference power, hence improving the signal-to-noise-plus-interference ratio (SINR). Additionally, the spatial dimension may be leveraged for the purposes of interference avoidance, i.e., directing signal energy towards the intended user and minimizing interference to other users. Interference reduction and avoidance improve the coverage and range of a wireless network. In general, it may not be possible to exploit simultaneously all the benefits described

above due to conflicting demands on the spatial degrees of freedom.

1.2 MIMO IN CELLULAR NETWORKS

In a cellular wireless communication network, multiple users may communicate at the same time and (or) frequency. The more aggressive the reuse of time and frequency resources, the higher the network capacity will be, provided that transmitted signals can be detected reliably. Multiple users may be separated in time (time-division) or frequency (frequency-division) or code (code-division). The spatial dimension in MIMO channels provides an extra dimension to separate users, allowing more aggressive reuse of time and frequency resources, thereby increasing the network capacity.

Fig1. MIMO cellular system. A base-station with L antennas communicates with P users, each equipped with M antennas.

Fig1 is the schematic of a cell in a MIMO cellular network. A base-station equipped with L antennas communicates with P users, each equipped with M antennas. The channel from the base-station to the users (the downlink) is a broadcast channel (BC) while the channel from the users to the base-station (the uplink) is a multiple-access channel (MAC). The set of rate-tuples (R_1, R_2, \dots, R_P) that can be reliably supported on the downlink or uplink constitutes the capacity rate region for that link. Recently, an important duality has been discovered between the rate regions for the downlink and uplink

Channels differences between users. However, with rich scattering and $L \geq PM$, we can expect that the spatial signatures of the users are well separated to allow reliable detection. Using a multi-user ZF receiver will allow perfect separation of all the data streams at the base-station, yielding a multi-user multiplexing gain of PM. The use of more complex receivers for multi-user detection and the associated

performance trade-offs. A similar thought experiment can be applied for the downlink, where the base-station exploits the spatial dimension to beam information intended for a particular user towards that user and steers nulls in the directions of the other users, thus completely eliminating interference.

1.3 DISTRIBUTED MIMO

While MIMO technology provides substantial performance gains, the cost of deploying multiple antennas at terminals in a network can be prohibitive, at least for the immediate future. Distributed MIMO is a means of realizing the gains of MIMO with single-antenna terminals in a network, allowing a gradual migration to a true MIMO network. The approach requires some level of cooperation between network terminals.

Fig.2. Distributed MIMO: multiple users cooperate to form a virtual antenna array that realizes the gains of MIMO in a distributed fashion

II. EXISTING SYSTEM

The effects of atmospheric and misalignment fading are analyzed in the case of single input single-output (SISO) FSO channels. Atmospheric turbulence fades the signal intensity at the receiver giving rise to turbulence-induced scintillation. The outage capacity of SISO is analyzed by effects of atmospheric turbulence and misalignment.

DISADVANTAGES

- Diversity Gain is reduced
- It is used for single input and single output i.e. one transmit and one receive antenna.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Fig. 3. Detector and beam footprint for transmitter #1 with misalignment at the detector plane.

Fig. 3 shows the block diagram of the system. A statistical model for MIMO FSO channels where both atmospheric and misalignment fading are considered. The outage capacity is analyzed by considering an intensity-modulated laser with pulse-amplitude-modulation (PAM). Diversity gain is analyzed using a log-normal distribution for the atmospheric fading. The outage probabilities are derived by taking account of different misalignment fading.

A) TECHNIQUE

Free space optics Free-space optical communication (FSO) is an optical communication technology that uses light propagating in free space to transmit data for telecommunications or computer networking. "Free space" means air, outer space, vacuum, or something similar. This contrasts with using solids such as optical fiber cable or an optical transmission line. The technology is useful where the physical connections are impractical due to high costs or other considerations.

Free-space point-to-point optical links can be implemented using infrared laser light, although low-data-rate communication over short distances is possible using LEDs. Infrared Data Association (IrDA) technology is a very simple form of free-space optical communications. Free Space Optics is additionally used for communications between spacecraft. Maximum range for terrestrial links is in the order of 2 to 3 km (1.2 to 1.9 mi), but the stability and quality of the link is highly dependent on atmospheric factors such as rain, fog, dust and heat. Amateur radio operators have achieved significantly farther distances using incoherent sources of light from high-intensity LEDs.

MIMO: Multiple-input and multiple-output (MIMO) is the use of multiple antennas at both the transmitter and receiver to improve communication performance. It is one of several forms of smart antenna technology. It offers significant increases in data throughput and link range without additional bandwidth or increased transmit power.

B) MODULES NAME

Channel Model

- Atmospheric and Misalignment Fading

Statistical MIMO FSO Channel Model

- Statistical Channel Model

Probability Of Outage And Diversity Gain

- Asymptotic Channel Capacity at High SNR
- Probability of Outage with Misalignment

Diversity Gain of MIMO FSO Channels

- Diversity Gain of MIMO FSO Channels
- Unidirectional Misalignment
- No Misalignment

C) Module Explanation: Channel Models

The model considers MIMO FSO system with M transmitters (lasers) and N receivers (apertures). In all cases, intensity modulated PAM signaling with direct detection is considered.

The received $N \times 1$ vector $y = [y_1, \dots, y_N]^T$ is given by

$$y = H^T x + z$$

where H is an $M \times N$ channel matrix where the entry $H_{mn} \geq 0$ represents the channel gain from transmitter m to receiver n with $m=1, \dots, M$ and $n = 1, \dots, N$ and $(\cdot)^T$ is the transpose operator. The vector $x = [x_1, \dots, x_M]^T$ is the transmitted set of symbols and $z = [z_1, \dots, z_N]^T$ is a noise vector of independent components modeled as signal independent white and Gaussian distributed.

The signal-to-noise ratio is defined as $SNR = P/\sigma$ and the channel gain

$$H = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^N H_{mn}$$

accounts for the combined effects of atmosphere and misalignment fading where

$$H_{mn} = H_{mn}^a H_{mn}^p$$

where H_{mn}^a and H_{mn}^p are independent random variables representing the atmospheric and time

varying misalignment (pointing) fading respectively between transmitter m and receiver n.

In the weak turbulence regime the channel gain due to atmospheric turbulence is well modeled by

$$H_{mn}^a = e^{X_{mn}}$$

where X_{mn} is a Gaussian random variable. Assume that all X_{mn} are modeled as independent and identically distributed (i.i.d) random variables.

For a radial displacement of R_{mn} in the receiver plane between the center of transmitter beam m and the center of aperture n, the loss due to misalignment is

$$H_{mn}^p \approx A_0 e^{-2R_{mn}^2/w^2}$$

where A_0 is the equivalent receiver area and w is the equivalent beam waist at receiver.

IV. STATISTICAL MIMO FSO CHANNEL MODEL

Misalignment fading depends on the geometric arrangement of the transmit lasers and receive apertures. In this work, we consider $M = N$. The spacing between transmit lasers is d which is also the spacing between receiver apertures. Note that d is assumed to be larger than the coherence length of atmospheric fading. We further assume that initially each transmit laser is aligned to the corresponding receive aperture. Let \mathcal{P} denote the set of coordinates of all receiver apertures. Also, let $P_n \in \mathcal{P}$ denote the coordinate vector of the nth receiver and Q_m denote the coordinate vectors of the center of the mth transmit beam footprint at the receiver plane. Thus, the beam footprint at the receiver for a random displacement of X' in the x-direction and Y' in the y-direction is

$$Q_m = \begin{bmatrix} X' \\ Y' \end{bmatrix} + P_m$$

for the case of no misalignment $P_m = Q_m$.

Statistical Channel Model

The channel gain between transmitter m and receiver n is given by

$$H_{mn} = H_{mn}^a H_{mn}^p = A_0 e^{X_{mn} - 2R_{mn}^2/w^2}$$

The total channel gain is given by

$$H = A_0 e^{-T} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^N e^{X_{mn} - U_{mn}}$$

D) PROBABILITY OF OUTAGE AND DIVERSITY GAIN

Since the coherence time of the FSO channel fading is much larger than the symbol duration, a slow-fading model is considered in the analysis. The outage probability is used as a performance metric and the diversity gain for $M = N$ transmitters and receivers is computed for a variety of spatial arrangements and misalignments.

Asymptotic Channel Capacity at High SNR

Consider a PAM modulated IM/DD FSO communication system subject to amplitude non-negativity and average constraints. Although a closed form is not known, at high SNR the asymptotic channel capacity can be efficiently bounded. The capacity of FSO channel is upper bounded as

$$C(SNR) \leq \log_2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{e}{2\pi}} SNR + 2 \right)$$

Considering an arbitrary input distribution in the mutual information expression results in a capacity lower bound. A lower bound on $C(SNR)$, (bits/channel use), can be developed in terms of mutual information I and entropy H as

$$C(SNR) \geq I(X; Y | H = h)_{f_X(x) \triangleq exp}$$

$$C(SNR) \approx \log_2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{e}{2\pi}} SNR \right)$$

Probability of Outage with Misalignment

For a given transmission rate, there is a finite probability that the transmitted rate exceeds the instantaneous mutual information of the channel. This probability is denoted as the outage probability and at a given rate R_0 is defined as

$$P_{out}(R_0) = Prob(C < R_0)$$

Consider the optical channel corrupted by atmospheric and misalignment fading, the outage probability at high SNR is given by

$$C(SNR) \leq \log_2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{e}{2\pi}} SNR + 2 \right)$$

$$P_{out}(R_0) = Prob_{f_H(h)} \left[\log_2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{e}{2\pi}} SNR \right) < R_0 \right]$$

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

Fig. 4. Probability of outage versus SNR for 2×2 and 4×4 MIMO FSO systems arranged as $\mathcal{P}2 \times 2$ and $\mathcal{P}4 \times 4$ resp. with unidirectional misalignment fading.

Fig. 5. Closed-form expression of the probability of outage versus SNR for 2×2 and 4×4 MIMO FSO systems with different atmospheric fading parameter.

Fig.6 Probability of outage versus SNR for 4×4 MIMO FSO system $\sigma_s^2=0.3, 0.1$ and 0.01 .

Fig.7 Probability of outage versus SNR for 2×2 and 4×4 MIMO FSO systems arranged as $\mathcal{P}2 \times 2$ and $\mathcal{P}4 \times 4$ respectively with symmetric misalignment fading.

Fig. 8. Probability of outage versus SNR for 1×1 SISO, 2×2 , 4×4 and 6×6 MIMO FSO systems.

Fig. 9. Probability of outage versus SNR for 1×1 SISO, 2×2 , and 4×4 MIMO FSO systems.

Advantages of Proposed System

- Increasing the diversity gain
- Misalignment fading is reduced

VI. CONCLUSIONS

A novel generalized statistical model for MIMO FSO channels impaired by atmospheric and misalignment fading is developed. The derived model is utilized to study the outage probability of FSO channels and the diversity gain at high signal-to-noise ratio. Closed-form expressions for the outage probability are derived taking into account different misalignment fading scenarios.

It is shown that, in the presence of atmospheric and misalignment fading, the diversity gain depends only on the misalignment parameters and is independent of both the number of transceivers and atmospheric fading parameters. Contrarily, when atmospheric fading is the only channel impairment, i.e., no misalignment fading, the diversity gain depends on the number of transceivers. Thus a larger diversity gain can be achieved by increasing the number of transmitters and receivers. In all cases increasing the number of transmitters and receivers decreases the outage probability for a given SNR. However, in order to have independent channels gains it is required to sufficiently increase the spacing between receivers which is often practically difficult.

An alternative approach is to utilize a large single-aperture with the equivalent area of the N apertures. This approach provides simple system structure and reduces the fading variance via aperture averaging. Note that, in this case the fading is correlated across the aperture and hence its variance is larger than that of a system with multiple apertures and independent fading at each aperture.

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BIOGRAPHY

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Grid Connected solar Reconfigurable Converter With energy storage PV- battery system

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ABSTRACT

Compared to the traditional energy resources, photovoltaic (PV) system that uses the solar energy to produce electricity considered as one of renewable energies has a great potential and developing increasingly fast compared to its counterparts of renewable energies. Such systems can be either stand-alone or connected to utility grid. However, the disadvantage is that PV generation depended on weather conditions. Thus, the battery energy storage is necessary to help get a stable and reliable output from PV generation system for loads and improve both steady and dynamic behaviors of the entire generation system. This paper presents detailed modeling of the grid-connected solar reconfigurable converter with energy storage PV/ Battery system components, in Simulink/ MATLAB software.

Keywords: converter, Reconfigurable solar Converter (RSC), photo voltaic (PV), MPPT, Solar power generation, PWM inverter.

I. INTRODUCTION

Solar photovoltaic (PV) electricity generation is not available and sometimes less available depending on the time of the day and the weather conditions. Solar PV electricity output also highly sensitive to shading. When even a small portion of a cell, module or array is shaded, while the remainder is in sunlight, the output falls dramatically. Therefore, solar PV electricity output significantly varies. As a result, energy storage such as batteries and fuel cells for solar PV systems has drawn significant attention and the demand of energy storage for solar PV systems has been dramatically increased. Since, with energy storage, a solar PV system becomes a stable energy source and it can be dispatched at the request, which results in improving the performance and the value of solar PV systems.

There are different options for integrating energy storage in to a utility-scale solar PV system. Especially energy storage can be possible either AC side or DC side of the solar PV power conversion systems which may consist of multiple stages. Every integration system has some advantages and as well as disadvantages compared with regard to

the number of power conversion stages, efficiency, and storage system flexibility, control complexity.

This paper introduces a novel single stage solar converter called as solar reconfigurable converter (SRC). The basic function of SRC is to use a single stage energy conversion system to perform five operating modes. Such as PV to Grid (mode1), PV to battery (mode2), PV and battery to Grid (mode3), battery to Grid (mode4) and Grid to battery (mode5). This converter solution is appealing for PV-battery application, because it minimizes the no of conversion stages, thereby improving efficiency and reducing cost, weight and volume.

II. SOLAR RECONFIGURABLE CONVERTER (SRC)

The SRC has some modifications to the conventional three-phase PV system. These modifications allow the SRC to include charging function in the conventional three-phase inverter system. SRC consist of voltage source inverter with charging and discharging energy storage device. Such as Li-ION battery and it requires additional cables and mechanical switches as shown in fig1. Optional

inductors are included if the AC filter inductance is not enough for the charging purpose. Inductance value of a coupled three-phase inductor in the DC/DC operation is as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Values of coupled three-phase inductances.

DC Application	Inductance Value
Only A	1.42mH
Only B	1.58mH
A&C	0.50mH
A&B&C	0.13mH

III. BENEFITS WITH SRC CONCEPT

The SRC concept allows not only the system owners to possess an expandable asset that helps them to plan and operate the power plant accordingly but also manufactures to offer cost-competitive decentralized PV energy storage solutions with the SRC and the current state of the art technology. The technical and financial benefits that the SRC is able to provide more apparent in larger solar PV power using the SRC's can be controlled more effectively and its power can be dispatched more economically, because of the flexibility of operation.

However different system controls can be proposed based on the requested power from the grid operator P_{req} and available generated power from the plant P_{gen} . In other words, in response to the request of the grid operator, different system control schemes can be realized with the SRC based solar plant as follows.

- 1) System control 1 for $P_{gen} > P_{req}$
- 2) System control 2 for $P_{gen} < P_{req}$
- 3) System control 3 for $P_{gen} = P_{req}$
- 4) System control 4 for charging from the grid

IV. OPERATING MODES OF SRC

There are five modes of operation of SRC. In Mode 1, the PV is directly connected to the grid through a dc/ac operation of the converter with possibility of maximum power point tracking (MPPT) control and the S1 and S6 switches remain open. In Mode 2, the battery is charged with the PV panels through the

dc/dc operation of the converter by closing the S6 switch and opening the S5 switch. In this mode, the MPPT function is performed; therefore, maximum power is generated from PV. There is another mode that both the PV and battery provide the power to the grid by closing the S1 switch. This operation is shown as Mode 3. In this mode, the dc-link voltage that is the same as the PV voltage is enforced by the battery voltage; therefore, MPPT control is not possible. Mode 4 represents an operation mode that the energy stored in the battery is delivered to the grid. There is another mode, Mode 5 that the battery is charged from the grid.

V. DESIGNING MODIFICATIONS TO THE CONVENTIONAL THREE PHASE CONVERTER

One of the most important requirements is that a new power conversion solution for PV-battery systems must have minimal complexity and modifications to the conventional three-phase solar PV converter system. It is common to use LCL filter for a high- power three-phase PV converter and the SRC in DC/DC operation is to use the inductors already available in the LCL filter. Here there are two types of inductors. One coupled three-phase inductors and three-phase inductors which are used in SRC circuit.

VI. SINUSOIDAL PWM TECHNIQUE

The sinusoidal pulse-width modulation (SPWM) technique produces a sinusoidal waveform by filtering an output pulse waveform with varying width. A high switching frequency leads to a better filtered sinusoidal output waveform. The desired output voltage is achieved by varying the frequency and amplitude of a reference or modulating voltage. The variations in the amplitude and frequency of the reference voltage change the pulse-width patterns of the output voltage but keep the sinusoidal modulation.

As shown in Fig. 2, a low-frequency sinusoidal modulating waveform is compared with a high-frequency triangular waveform, which is called the carrier waveform. The switching state is changed when the sine waveform intersects the triangular waveform. The crossing positions determine the variable switching times between states. In three-phase SPWM, a triangular voltage waveform (V_T) is compared with three sinusoidal control voltages (V_a , V_b , and V_c), which are 120° out of phase with each

other and the relative levels of the waveforms are used to control the switching of the devices in each phase leg of the inverter.

A six-step inverter is composed of six switches S1 through S6 with each phase output connected to the middle of each inverter leg as shown in Figure 5.2. The output of the comparators in Figure 2.1 forms the control signals for the three legs of the inverter. Two switches in each phase make up one leg and open and close in a complementary fashion. That is, when one switch is open, the other is closed and vice-versa. The output pole voltages V_{ao}, V_{bo}, and V_{co} of the inverter switch between -V_{dc}/2 and +V_{dc}/2 voltage levels where V_{dc} is the total DC voltage. The peak of the sine modulating waveform is always less than the peak of the triangle carrier voltage waveform. When the sinusoidal waveform is greater than the triangular waveform, the upper switch is turned on and the lower switch is turned off. Similarly, when the sinusoidal waveform is less than the triangular waveform, the upper switch is off and the lower switch is on. Depending on the switching states, either the positive or negative half DC bus voltage is applied to each phase. The switches are controlled in pairs((S1;S4), (S3;S6), and (S5;S2)) and the logic for the switch control signals is:

_ S1 is ON when V_a>V_T S4 is ON when V_a<V_T
 _ S3 is ON when V_b>V_T S6 is ON when V_b<V_T
 _ S5 is ON when V_c>V_T S2 is ON when V_c<V_T

The pulse widths depend on the intersection of the triangular and sinusoidal waveforms. The inverter output voltages are determined as follows:

if V_a>V_T then V_{ao} = 0.5V_{dc}
 V_b>V_T then V_{bo} = 0.5V_{dc}
 V_c>V_T then V_{co} = 0.5V_{dc}.

The modulation index is defined as the ratio of the magnitude of output voltage generated by SPWM to the fundamental peak value of the maximum square wave. Thus, the maximum modulation index of the SPWM technique is

$$MI = \frac{V_{pwm}}{V_{max} - \text{sixstep}} = \frac{V_{dc}/2}{2V_{dc}/\pi} = \frac{1}{4} = 0.7855 = 78.55\%$$

VII. MODELING OF SOLAR PANEL

The current generated by a PV Cell can be given as in eqn 1. Including the series and parallel resistances

$$= N_p I_{ph} - N_p I_s \left[\exp\left(\frac{q(V/N_s + I R_s)}{k T C_A}\right) - 1 \right] - \left[\frac{N_p V / N_s + I R_s}{R_{sh}} \right]$$

(1)

where

I_{ph} is the photovoltaic current, I_o is the diode saturation currents of the array, R_s is the series resistance of the array, R_{sh} is the parallel resistance of the array, T_c is the cells temperature constant, N_s is cells connected in series, N_p is cells connected in parallel, q is the electron charge [1.60217646 *10⁻¹⁹C], k is the Boltzmann constant [1.3806503 * 10⁻²³J/K], T is the temperature of the p-n junction.

Mainly to model a solar cell, the only value to be found is the output current, I. This current is calculated as I=I_{pv} - I_d, where I_{pv} is the photo generated current and I_d is the diode current. Modeling of diode current as shown in Fig. 3.

Parameters of the Solar Module

Table 2. Parameters of BPSX 150s Solar array at Standard test conditions

Current at Max. Power point, I _{mp} =4.35A
Voltage at max. Power point, V _{mp} =34.5V
Max. Output Power of a single module, P _{max} =150W
Short Circuit current of module, I _{sc} =4.75 A
Open Circuit voltage of module V _{oc} =43.5 V
Voltage temperature coefficient, K _v =-80e-3 V/K
Current temperature coefficient K _i =0.003 A/K
Number of cells connected in series, N _s =36
Parallel Resistance, R _p = 150.9 Ω
Series Resistance, R _s = 0.35 Ω
Ideality factor, a = 1.99

VIII. SIMULATION RESULTS

Few simulation results are shown in Fig. 7 to 11.

Fig7. SRC without filter

Fig. 8. PV and IV graphs of solar module

Fig.9. PV to Grid (mode1)

Fig. 10. Battery to Grid(mode4)

Fig. 11. PV and Battery to grid (mode3)

IX. CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduced a new converter called SRC for PV-battery application, particularly utility-scale PV-battery application. The concept of the SRC is to use a single power conversion system to perform different operation modes such as PV to grid (dc to ac), PV to battery (dc to dc), battery to grid (dc to ac), and battery/PV to grid (dc to ac) for solar PV systems with energy storage. by using SPWM. The proposed solution requires minimal complexity and modifications to the three-phase solar PV converters for PV-battery systems. Therefore, the solution is very attractive for PV-battery application, because it minimizes the number of conversion stages, thereby improving efficiency and reducing cost, weight, and volume.

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Fig. 1. Solar Reconfigurable Converter.

Fig2. Sinusoidal PWM technique.

Fig. 3. Modelling of diode current equation.

Fig. 4. Simulation of SRC without filter.

Fig. 5. Simulation of SRC circuit with filter.

Fig. 6. Simulation of PV array.

Optimal Linear Transmit Beam Forming Techniques for Multi-User MIMO

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ABSTRACT

Adaptive transmit beam forming is key to increased spectral and energy efficiency in next-generation wireless networks. In light of the difficulty to compute the optimal multiuser transmit beam forming there is a plethora of heuristic schemes. Transmit beam forming is a versatile technique for signal transmission from an array of N antennas to one or multiple users. In wireless communications, the goal is to increase the signal power at the intended user and reduce interference to non-intended users. A high signal power is achieved by transmitting the same data signal from all antennas. Since transmit beam forming focuses the signal energy at certain places, less energy arrives to other places. This allows for so-called space-division multiple accesses (SDMA), where K spatially separated users are served simultaneously. One beam forming vector is assigned to each user and can be matched to its channel. Unfortunately, the finite number of transmit antennas only provides a limited amount of spatial directivity, which means that there are energy leakages between the users which act as interference. To design a beam forming vector that maximizes the signal power at the intended user, it is difficult to strike a perfect balance between maximizing the signal power and minimizing the interference leakage.

Keywords: SDMA; Transmit Beam form in; SNIR and Power minimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Multi-input multi-output (MIMO) communications systems have attracted high spectral efficiency. In point-to-point multiple antenna systems is well known that the capacity increases linearly with the minimum of the number of transmit/receive antennas, irrespective of the availability of channel state information (CSI) at the base station.

The multi-user MIMO downlink refers to where multi-antenna transmitter simultaneously communicates with several co-channel users. Only recently has the multi-user MIMO downlink been addressed, beginning with information-theoretic capacity results [1–5], and followed by practical

implementations, including those based on linear techniques [6, 7] and non-linear pre coding [8–11].

The problem of meeting quality of services (QoS) constraints with minimum transmit power is often referred to as the downlink power control or interference-balancing problem. As with sum capacity maximization, channel knowledge at the transmitter is crucial to finding a solution Channel state information is most often obtained by means of uplink training data, as in a time-division duplex system, or via feedback from the users, as in the frequency-division duplex case. Each approach has its advantages and disadvantages in terms of throughput penalty and latency.

CSI can be in the form of deterministic channel estimates, or it can be described in probabilistic terms (e.g., channel mean and covariance). While we will focus on the deterministic case in this chapter, statistical CSI may be directly applied in most cases. For an excellent and comprehensive treatment of the issues involved with different types of CSI.

In line-of-sight (LOS) between the transmitter and receiver, beam forming can be seen as forming a signal beam toward the receiver. Figure.1 Beam forming can also be applied in non-LOS scenarios, if the multipath channel is known, by making the multipath components add coherently or destructively. Since transmit beam forming focuses the signal energy at certain places, less energy arrives to other places. This allows for so-called space-division multiple access (SDMA), where K spatially separated users are served simultaneously. One beam forming vector is assigned to each user and can be matched to its channel. Unfortunately, the finite number of transmit antennas only provides a limited amount of spatial directivity, which means that there are energy leakages between the users which act as interference. While it is fairly easy to design a beam forming vector that maximizes the signal power at the intended user, it is difficult to strike a perfect balance between maximizing the signal power and minimizing the interference leakage. In fact, the optimization of multiuser transmit beam forming is generally a nondeterministic polynomial-time (NP) hard problem.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. The next section we introduce the power minimization with signal to interference ratio. In the section III, we describe the results analysis and finally conclusions are drawn in section IV.

II. POWER MINIMIZATION WITH SINR

We consider a downlink channel where a base station (BS) equipped with N antennas communicates with K single-antenna users using SDMA. The data signal to user k is denoted $P_k \in \mathbb{C}$ and is normalized to unit power, while the vector $h_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ describes the corresponding channel. The K different data signals are separated spatially using the linear beam forming vectors w_1, w_2, \dots, w_K where w_k is associated with user k.

Fig. 1. Visualization of transmit beam forming in an LOS scenario.

The received signal at k user as

$$y_k = h_k^H \left(\sum_{i=1}^K w_i P_i \right) + z_k \quad (1)$$

Where z_k is additive receiver noise with zero mean and variance σ^2 consequently, the signal-to-noise and- interference ratio (SINR) at user k is

$$SINR_k = \frac{|h_k^H w_k|^2}{\sum_{i \neq k} |h_k^H w_i|^2 + \sigma^2} = \frac{\frac{1}{\sigma^2} |h_k^H w_k|^2}{\sum_{i \neq k} \frac{1}{\sigma^2} |h_k^H w_i|^2 + 1} \quad (2)$$

The transmit beam forming can be optimized to maximize some performance utility metric, which is generally a function of the SINRs. We first solve the relatively simple power minimization problem

$$\min_{w_1, \dots, w_K} \sum_{k=1}^K \|w_k\|^2 \quad (3)$$

$$SINR_k \geq \gamma_k \quad (4)$$

The parameters $\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_K$ are the SINRs that each user shall achieve at the optimum of (4), using as little transmit power as possible. The γ -parameters can, for example, describe the SINRs required for achieving certain data rates. The absolute values in the SINRs in (2) make w_k and $e^{j\theta_k}$ completely equivalent for any common phase rotation $\theta_k \in \mathbb{R}$. Without loss of optimality, we exploit this phase ambiguity to rotate the phase such that the inner product $h_k^H w_k$ is real-valued and positive.

This implies that $\sqrt{|h_k^H w_k|^2} = h_k^H w_k \geq 0$.

By letting $\Re(\cdot)$ denoting the real part, the constraint $SINR_k \geq \gamma_k$ can be rewritten as

$$\frac{1}{\gamma\sigma^2} |h_k^H w_k|^2 \geq \sum_{i \neq k} \frac{1}{\sigma^2} |h_k^H w_i|^2 + 1 \Leftrightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{\gamma_k \sigma^2}} \Re(h_k^H w_k) \geq \sqrt{\sum_{i \neq k} \frac{1}{\sigma^2} |h_k^H w_i|^2 + 1} \quad (5)$$

The reformulated SINR constraint in (5) is a second-order cone constraint, which is a convex type of constraint [10]–[12], and it is easy to show that Slater’s constraint qualification is fulfilled [13].

Hence, optimization theory provides many important properties for the reformulated convex problem; in particular, strong duality and that the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) conditions are necessary and sufficient for the optimal solution. The optimal beam forming vectors

$$w_k^* = \sqrt{p} \frac{\left(I_N + \sum_{i=1}^K \frac{\lambda_i}{\sigma^2} h_i h_i^H \right)^{-1} h_k}{\left\| \left(I_N + \sum_{i=1}^K \frac{\lambda_i}{\sigma^2} h_i h_i^H \right)^{-1} h_k \right\|} \quad (6)$$

For $k=1, 2, \dots, K$

$$= \sqrt{p_k} \cdot \hat{w}_k^* = \text{beam forming direction} \quad (7)$$

Where p_k denotes the beam forming power and \hat{w}_k^* denotes the unit-norm beam forming direction for user k . The K unknown beam forming powers are computed by noting that the SINR constraints (4) hold with equality at the optimal solution.

III. RESULTS ANALYSIS

In this section we provides the properties of Maximum Ratio Transmission (MRT), Zero Forcing Beam Forming (ZFBF), and transmit MMSE beam forming are illustrated by simulation in Figure 2. We consider $K = 4$ users with the sum rate as utility function:

$$f(SINR_1, \dots, SINR_4) = \sum_{k=1}^4 \log_2(1 + SINR_k) \quad (8)$$

Figure 2 shows the simulation results for (a) $N = 4$ and (b) $N = 12$ transmit antennas. In the former case, we observe that MRT is near-optimal at low SNRs, while ZFBF is asymptotically optimal at high- SNRs. Transmit MMSE beam forming is a more versatile scheme that combines the respective asymptotic properties of MRT and ZFBF with good performance at intermediate SNRs. However, there is still a significant gap to the optimal solution, which is only bridged by fine-tuning the $K = 4$ parameters $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_4$ (with an exponential complexity in K). In the case of $N = 12$, there are many more antennas than users, which makes the need for fine-tuning much smaller; transmit MMSE beam forming is near optimal in the entire SNR range.

Fig. 2. Average sum rate for $K = 4$ users as a function of the average SNR.

Heuristic beam forming can perform closely to the optimal beam forming, particularly when there are many more antennas than users. Transmit MMSE/regularized ZFBF always performs better, or equally well, as MRT and ZFBF.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The optimal beam forming maximizes the received signal powers at low SNRs, minimizes the interference leakage at high SNRs, and balances between these conflicting goals at intermediate SNRs. In this paper describes the optimal beam forming structure can be extended to practical multi-cell scenarios. Alternative beam forming parameterizations based on local channel state information (CSI) or transceiver hardware impairments can be found. Some open problems in this field are the robustness to imperfect CSI, multi-stream beam forming to multi-antenna users, multi-casting where each signal is intended for a group of users.

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